

SEADE

STRENGTHENING THE
EUROPE-AFRICA
DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM
THROUGH INCREASED
R&I COOPERATION

Deliverable 4.1

Report on the SEADE expansion activities

Partner(s):

LEADER: BOND

Participants: MET, HAPA, WAZI, EiAC, BPI, EBN, TIA, AAU, S2i

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

Document Control Sheet

Project Acronym	SEADE
Project Full Name	Strengthening the Europe-Africa Digital Ecosystem Through Increased R&I Cooperation
Grant Agreement No.	101135194
Instrument	HORIZON Coordination and Support Action
Start Date of Project	01/01/2024
Duration	24 months
Work Package	WP4
Associated Task	T4.1, T4.2
Type	R — Document, report
Due Date	31/12/2025
Actual Submission	12/12/2025
Lead Organisation	BOND

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Description
1	December 2024	BOND, HAPA, MET, WAZI	Webinar report integrated and validated by BOND
2	January 2025	BOND	Senegal softlanding report integrated
3	February 2025	HAPA	Ghana Learning Expedition report integrated
4	February 2025	MET	South Africa Learning Expedition report integrated

5	Between March and October 2025	All partners	Other activities reports integrated
6	October 2025	BOND	Global review, shortening of the report and feedback to other partners to harmonize the deliverable
7	November 2025	All partners	Feedback integration
8	November 2025	BOND	Finalization of the deliverable
9	December 2025	S2i	Final review before submission

Executive Summary

This document outlines the methodology and the takeaways of “Route-to-Market” capacity building programmes of the EU-funded SEADE project, implemented and delivered to research and innovation actors within the four pilot-regions (Senegal, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa) and beyond. Based on the gaps identified through previous research conducted, the pilot leads of the four pilot regions implemented activities and programmes to build bridges and facilitate collaboration between European and sub-Saharan African R&IID actors.

In this respect, this report presents an overview of the programmes implemented and the support provided to the participants. Each pilot region implemented a webinar, a learning expedition and a soft landing programme. In addition, bootcamp sessions were organised and a Digital Youth Training Programme was developed and implemented in Kenya. A twinning programme and matchmaking activities with investors were also implemented.

This diversity and complementarity of activities has helped to generate interest and mobilise R&IID actors; strengthen the capacities of R&IID actors in European and sub-Saharan Africa; initiate and structure collaborations between them; open up funding opportunities; and promote and raise the profile of the pilot regions in the international R&IID ecosystem. This report also presents an opportunity to highlight the best practices identified and implemented for each activity.

We can highlight a majority interest on the part of actors in sub-Saharan Africa, whereas it was more challenging to mobilise European actors in the context of the activities implemented. Furthermore, obtaining visas and mobilising female and rural actors were challenges encountered across all pilot regions.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary..... 4

Table of Contents..... 5

Introduction.....9

Work Implemented And Results..... 10

A. Webinars..... 11

1. Overall presentation and timeline.....11

2. Deviations from workplan..... 11

3. Senegalese webinar.....11

4. Kenyan webinar..... 13

5. Ghanaian webinar..... 13

6. South African webinar..... 14

7. Overall results and achievements..... 16

8. Users’ survey feedback.....17

B. Learning Expeditions..... 17

1. Overall presentation.....17

2. Deviations from workplan..... 17

3. Senegalese Learning Expedition..... 17

- Deviations from workplan..... 18
- Timeline..... 18
- Learning Expedition implementation programme..... 19
- Results, achievements and best practices..... 20
- Users’ survey feedback..... 20
- Best practices identified and challenges met..... 20

4. Kenyan Learning Expeditions.....21

- Deviations from workplan..... 22
- Program Agenda..... 22
- Results, achievements and best practices..... 24
- Users’ survey feedback..... 25
- Best practices identified and challenges met..... 25

5. Ghanaian Learning Expeditions..... 25

- Deviations from the workplan..... 26
- Timeline..... 26
- Learning Expedition programme..... 26
- Results, achievements and best practices..... 27
- Users’ survey feedback..... 28
- Best practices identified and challenges met..... 29

6. South African Learning Expedition..... 29

- Deviations from the workplan..... 29

- Timeline..... 30
- Learning Expedition programme..... 31
- Results, achievements and best practices..... 32
- Users’ survey feedback..... 32
- Best practices identified and challenges met..... 33
- C. Softlanding Programmes..... 34**
 - 1. Overall presentation..... 34
 - 2. Deviations from workplan..... 34
 - 3. Senegalese Softlanding..... 35
 - Specific deviations from the workplan..... 35
 - Timeline..... 35
 - Softlanding programme..... 36
 - Results and achievements..... 38
 - Users’ survey feedback..... 39
 - Best practices identified and challenges met..... 39
 - 4. Kenyan Softlanding..... 40
 - Program Overview and Requirements with Timeline..... 40
 - Deviations from workplan..... 40
 - Program Agenda..... 40
 - Execution..... 41
 - Results and achievements..... 42
 - Users’ survey feedback:..... 43
 - Best practices identified and challenges met..... 43
 - 5. Ghanaian Softlanding..... 44
 - Specific deviations from the workplan..... 44
 - Timeline..... 44
 - Softlanding programme..... 46
 - Results and achievements..... 47
 - Users’ survey feedback..... 48
 - Best practices identified and challenges met..... 48
 - 6. South African Softlanding..... 49
 - Specific deviations from the workplan..... 50
 - Timeline..... 51
 - Specific deviations from the workplan..... 52
 - Softlanding Programme..... 53
 - Results, achievements and best practices..... 54
 - Users’ survey feedback..... 54
 - Best practices identified and challenges met..... 55
- D. Bootcamp training programme..... 56**
 - 1. Overall presentation and timeline..... 56

2. Deviations from workplan..... 57

3. Navigating Challenges that limit market access for R&IID Innovations in Europe and Africa... 57

4. Funding Pathways and Practical Strategies for Research & Innovation Actors.....58

5. Strategies for Youth and Women Empowerment in Digital R&I..... 59

6. A Playbook for Research and Innovation Investment: How to Engage Investors and Raise Investment..... 60

7. How-to Connect and Develop a Successful Collaboration between EU-SSA Actors..... 61

8. Overall results and achievements..... 62

9. Users’ survey feedback..... 63

E. Digital Youth Training programme.....63

1. Program Overview and Requirements with Timeline.....63

2. Deviations from workplan..... 64

3. Pre-selection..... 64

4. Program Agenda..... 64

5. Execution and Results.....65

6. Results and achievements..... 66

7. Users’ survey feedback.....66

8. Best practices identified and challenges met..... 67

9. Translation of DYTP materials into Learning Curricula for Universities, The Wazilab platform - AIoT Route to market (RtoM) program..... 67

F. Twinning programme.....67

1. Overall presentation..... 67

2. Deviations from workplan..... 68

3. Timeline.....68

4. Program Timeline and Activities.....68

5. Call for application.....69

6. Selection.....69

7. Program Structure..... 70

8. Monitoring Process..... 70

1. Results and achievements..... 71

1. Users’ survey feedback..... 72

Main Positives Identified..... 72

11. Best practices and challenges met..... 72

G. R&I to Industry Match-Making Activities..... 72

1. Deviations from workplan..... 72

2. Overall timeline..... 73

3. Detail of the activities..... 73

- E-pitching sessions..... 73
- Process 74
- Results and achievements..... 74

• Reverse-pitches.....	75
• Results and achievements.....	76
4. Main results and achievements.....	77
• Overall results.....	77
• Satisfaction survey’s feedback.....	78
Conclusion.....	80

Introduction

This document details the activities of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the SEADE project, which is titled “Expansion of Offerings to foster EU & AU R&I cooperation in digital”.

The core objective of WP4 was to develop and implement new tools and a learning environment designed to support Research and Innovation (R&I) cooperation in the digital field, specifically by fostering knowledge development, knowledge transfer, and human mobility between the EU and Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). This goal was achieved through the implementation of "Route to market" activities, executed under Task 4.1 ("Route to market capacity building programmes") led by Bond'innov (BOND) and Task 4.2 ("R&I to Industry matchmaking activities") led by BpiFrance (BPI). The activities were implemented across the four pilot regions, Ghana, Senegal, Kenya and South Africa.

The SEADE project seeks to promote collaboration between EU and SSA R&IID actors. R&IID actors (Research and Innovation in Digital) includes research centers, university innovation centers, post graduate researchers, entrepreneurs, companies and startups, industries and policy makers.

The “Route to market” activities implemented under WP4 includes the following:

- **Webinars:** Aimed to provide key market knowledge development and exchange for international actors as they look to connect to, and collaborate with the pilot regions
- **Learning Expeditions:** Allowing EU and SSA R&IID attendees to explore the four pilot regions, their actors, markets, and success criteria, over a week-long programme.
- **Softlanding programmes:** Supporting the mobility of EU R&IID actors into pilot ecosystems over 3-months.
- **Bootcamp training programme:** To bring together EU and SSA R&IID and industry actors to upskill their capacity for bridging the gap between research and market success including training in market knowledge, business development and investment readiness
- **Youth Digital Training programme:** Ran in parallel to the ‘Route-to-Market’ pathway programmes supporting SSA young entrepreneurs, with a priority on women, researchers, students and the tech community, to create a startup or prototyping an idea for technology transfer.
- **Twinning programme:** It provided a framework for collaboration between Twinning pairs consisting of one European and one African R&IID actor, allowing them to travel in order to structure and consolidate their collaboration.
- **E-pitching sessions:** To establish investor contacts & ensure market expansion success for R&IID actors
- **Reverse pitch sessions:** served to present different types of funding and resources available to researchers and innovators when building companies.

These activities began at M6 and were ongoing until M24 for the Twinning Programme and Task 4.2 activities. Thus, Milestone 7, ‘Launch of the initial set of Route-to-market tools and services,’ was effective before M12.

Work Implemented And Results

This document presents in detail the design, preparation, implementation and results of each of the ‘Route to market’ activities, while maintaining a consolidated and harmonised structure despite the fact that the report for each activity was produced by the partner responsible for implementing that activity.

Thus, the results of each activity are presented in the dedicated report.

As far as the KPIs are concerned, please find below the main KPIs:

- 1 bootcamp Training programme organized with 211 participants
- 4 webinars organized with 149 participants
- 4 Learning Expeditions with 52 participants in total
- 4 softlanding programmes with 56 participants in total
- 4 twinning matches involving 8 participants
- 1 Digital Innovation Youth Training Programme with 20 participants
- 4 e-pitching events
- 4 reverse pitches

Route to market activity	Achievement
Bootcamp Training programme	1 organized with 211 participants
Webinars	4 organized with 149 participants
Learning Expeditions	4 organized with 52 participants
Softlanding programmes	4 organized with 56 participant
Twinning matches	4 matches involving 8 participants
Digital Innovation Youth Training Programme	1 organized with 20 participants
E-pitching Sessions	4 sessions organized
Reverse pitch Sessions	4 sessions organized

C. Webinars

1. Overall presentation and timeline

The webinars were designed as a series of webinars throughout October 2024 and implemented by the 4 pilot regions leaders (BOND, HAPA, WAZI, MET).

The aim of these webinars was to provide key market knowledge development and exchange for international actors as they look to connect to, and collaborate with, the pilot regions. 100 R&IID actors were expected to participate in order to meet the KPIs set.

Each pilot region leader organized a webinar. These webinars were organized online via Teams and recorded.

The themes of each webinar were as follows:

- **Senegal: Presentation of Senegal's research and innovation ecosystem (*Delivered on the 9th of October 2024*)**
- **Kenya: IoT AI Research 'Route to Market' program (*Delivered on the 16th of October 2024*)**
- **Ghana: Presentation of Ghana's research and innovation ecosystem (*Delivered on the 23th of October 2024*)**
- **South Africa : The State of Innovation in Africa: A South African Perspective (*Delivered on the 30th of October 2024*)**

A communications plan was launched at the end of September to promote the webinars via the SEADE LinkedIn page and the project website. Each of the pilot regions also communicated about this activity to their respective communities.

At the end of each webinar, each pilot region leader sent the users' survey form in order to gather feedback from participants, in accordance with Work Package 5 (Deliverable 5.1).

The complete Jotform survey is available via this link: <https://form.jotform.com/242756982838576>

2. Deviations from workplan

No deviation from the workplan.

3. Senegalese webinar

The Senegal pilot region webinar ("Senegal: Land of opportunity and innovation") took place on October 09, 2024 from 2pm GMT to 4:19pm GMT. It was hosted in French.

It highlighted Senegal's potential as an innovation hub in West Africa, showcasing its economic growth, key sectors and research and innovation initiatives. Opportunities offered by the

Senegalese market, Senegalese research infrastructures and potential partnerships for international players wishing to invert or establish a presence in Senegal were presented.

Ismaël Issoufou Issaka, project manager at Bond'innov and based in Senegal, was the webinar's speaker.

The webinar aimed to strengthen understanding of the Senegalese ecosystem and explored opportunities for collaboration in research and digital innovation between Europe and Africa. Here's an overview of the topics covered:

- **Senegal's general context:** The speaker began with a macro-economic presentation of Senegal, highlighting its strategic geographical position, its active role within ECOWAS and UEMOA, as well as its linguistic and economic assets. These elements underline Senegal's strengths as a gateway to a potential market of 302 million consumers.
- **Economic growth dynamics:** Senegal stands out for its solid post-COVID economic recovery and promising outlook. The webinar explored the key factors of its attractiveness, such as political stability, growing foreign investment and the contributions of the diaspora, which play a central role in the country's economic development.
- **Growth sectors:** The key sectors of the Senegalese economy were presented: primary resources (agriculture, fishing, livestock), secondary industries (energy, agri-food), and tertiary services, notably ICT, which open up interesting opportunities for digital innovation and international collaboration.
- **Research and digital innovation ecosystem:** The speaker delved deeper into Senegal's research and innovation framework, examining its infrastructure, government initiatives, international collaborations and the opportunities offered by available funding. The aim was to provide a comprehensive understanding of local dynamics and potential synergies.
- **Q&A session:** Finally, an interactive session gave participants the opportunity to ask questions and go into greater depth on the points discussed, thus fostering enriching exchanges. The question-and-answer session highlighted participants' interest in the various topics discussed, illustrating their desire to gain a better understanding of the Senegalese ecosystem and explore opportunities for collaboration.

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** 36 participants, 15 from Europe (41.7%), 18 from Africa (50.0%), and 3 from others (8.3%).
- **Organization types:** In terms of organization type, companies (39.4%) come out on top, followed by private innovation support organizations (27.3%).
- **Profiles of the participants:** The profiles of webinar participants are varied and highly qualitative. Those who stood out included 12 founders (33.3%) and 4 managing directors (11.1%).
- **Gender representation:** In terms of parity, the webinar recorded a total of 21 men (58.3%), 14 women (41.7%).

Besides, according to the users' survey completed by 10 participants, here are the satisfaction results:

- **Average satisfaction rate:** 80% of the respondents considered the webinars “Interesting” or “Of great interest”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 60% of the respondents considered the webinars fitted their needs “Well” or “Very well”.

4. Kenyan webinar

The Kenya webinar took place on the **16th of October 2024**. It involved key speakers from industry, university and internal consortium members from WAZIUP e.V. and Association of African Universities (AAU). The webinar was open to the public and had participants from Africa and Europe. This webinar was important as it was the launching point of the ‘SEADE IoT AI Route to Market program’, a packaged program to support IoT digital innovators in Kenya to build their solution development in IoT and transition them to market. This program contained a one week Learning Expedition, a one week Digital Youth Training program and an 12 week Soft-landing Mission program designed to support IoT innovators in their solution development. Overall, the program is designed to take 14 weeks.

The program had 4 key sessions: A welcome note and introduction from WAZIUP and AAU presentation of the IoT AI Route to Market program including an overview of the program model, description of each of the program modules and presentation of the WAZILAB platform and the tools and services it will provide to support young IoT innovators during their development phase. The final two sessions were insights from university and industry. It was used to provide the webinar participants with an overview of the Digital R&I IoT state in Kenya and some of the opportunities available for collaborations and partnerships.

The final session was a Q&A session from the participants of the program. The webinar lasted 2 hours from 10 am to 12 pm CET.

Here is the main information about the participants:

Number of participants: 49 participants.

Due to a technical problem (bug in Teams) the export of data of the participants for the Kenyan webinar was not possible, data could not be extracted.

According to the users’ survey completed by 3 participants after the webinar, here are the satisfaction results:

- **Average satisfaction rate:** 100% of the respondents considered the webinars “Interesting”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 33,3% of the respondents considered the webinars fit their needs “Well” and 66,7% “Well enough”.

5. Ghanaian webinar

The Ghanaian SEADE webinar “Presentation of Ghana’s research and innovation ecosystem”, moderated by Agyemeng Okyere Darko from the Association of African Universities (AAU), served as an engaging platform to reinforce SEADE’s mission of creating effective route-to-market pathways for research and innovation (R&I) actors across Africa.

The session opened with an overview by Philipina Beatrice Brefo, Head of Programs at hapaSpace, who introduced SEADE's vision of fostering collaborative, digital, and market-oriented opportunities between Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa. The keynote presentation by Dr. Peter Dok Tindan highlighted Ghana's emerging role in Africa's innovation ecosystem and its potential to lead in sustainable development. Drawing from his extensive experience in agricultural transformation, climate change, and sustainability, Dr. Tindan examined Ghana's historical economic evolution, growing innovation infrastructure, and the opportunities within its diverse sectors. His discussion underscored the significance of Ghana's policy reforms, expanding digital infrastructure, and the crucial role of innovation hubs in driving regional economic growth.

Dr. Tindan provided in-depth details of the Ghanaian R&IID environment, including Ghana's economic landscape, the multifaceted innovation ecosystem, the types of innovation hubs present, and the emerging research infrastructure. It also covers insights on collaboration opportunities, infrastructure challenges, and sustainable investment prospects, all aimed at bridging local innovations to global markets. Active audience engagement further enriched the session, with participants keenly exploring ways to adapt sustainable and scalable business models within their regions.

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** 35 participants, 5 from Europe (14,3%), 27 from Africa (77,1%), and 3 from others (8,6%).
- **Organization types:** Among the most represented types of structure, 16,7% of the participants were from Companies, 11,1% from Private innovation support organizations, 11,1% from Higher education institutes and 11,1% from Innovative SME/Startup.
- **Profiles of the participants:** The profiles of webinar participants are varied and highly qualitative. CEOs were the main profile represented with 14,3% of the participants.
- **Gender representation:** In terms of parity, the webinar recorded a total of 24 men (59%), 17 women (41%).

Besides, according to the users' survey completed by 2 participants, here are the satisfaction results:

- **Average satisfaction rate:** 50% of the respondents considered the webinars "Interesting" and 50% "Of great interest".
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 50% of the respondents considered the webinars fit their needs "Well" and 50% "Well enough".

6. South African webinar

The South Africa pilot region webinar ("The State of Innovation in Africa: A South African Perspective") took place on the 30th of October 2024 from 2pm SAST. The webinar was hosted by Thomas Hart from Methys and Zandile Ntuli from the Enrich in Africa Centre.

This webinar highlighted the State of Digital Innovation in Africa but with a focus on the South African market with an analysis on research and innovation within the digital economy of South Africa.

The webinar program was broken down as follows:

- **Africa's State of Digital Innovation:** Within this section of the presentation, Methys provided an analysis of the state of research and innovation in the digital and technology sectors of Africa and the impact of research and innovation infrastructure and resources.
- **South Africa: A Leader in Digital Innovation in Africa:** In the next section of the presentation, Methys provided an overview of why South Africa is a leader in research and innovation in Africa in comparison with the rest of South Africa. Methys presented data and insights on South Africa's economy, education and industries and then looked deeper into its digital economy and why it's been the leader in Africa in digital innovation.
- **South African Digital and ICT Policies and Initiatives** Methys provided an overview of South Africa's core digital and ICT policies that regulated the market in South Africa and where the opportunities lie in policy for cross border and continental collaboration and partnerships and where policy has failed and provided bottlenecks in innovation.
- **Challenges of Innovation within the Digital Sector of South Africa:** With the discussions on where South Africa succeeds in innovation and local policies that regulate the market, the audience then discussed the challenges that South Africa still experiences.
- **Opportunities of Innovation within the Digital Sector of South Africa:** The analysis of South Africa's state of innovation ended with an overview and analysis of where opportunities of growth and collaboration exist in the digital economy of South Africa in research and innovation. The webinar presentation ended with a call for action in terms of SEADE future go to market programs.
- **Panel:** For the panel discussion, Tendia Pasipamire from the Enrich in Africa Centre was the moderator and the time for the panel discussion was 20 minutes. The speakers for the panel discussion consisted of the following: Tendai Pasipamire (Enrich in Africa Centre), Thuli Montana (Briter Bridges), Mmampei Chaba (Department of Science & Innovation), Linda Lawrie (Propealla). Tendai, as the moderator, asked each speaker a set of questions based on the experience and knowledge in relation to the insights and finding of the State of Innovation in Africa: A South African Perspective webinar presentation.

Following the live broadcast of the webinar, Methys had a number of last minute applications for the South African Learning Expedition in which 2 audience members were selected and participated in the LEX in Cape Town on the 27th of November.

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** 39 participants, 6 from Europe (15,4%), 29 from Africa (74,4%), and 4 from others (10,2%).
- **Organization types:** In terms of organization type, Companies representatives were the most represented (25%), followed by Higher education institutes (17,5%), Digital innovation hubs (12,5%) and Private innovation support organizations (10%).
- **Profiles of the participants:** The profiles of webinar participants are varied and highly qualitative. Those who stood out included: Founders (10%), CEO (7,5%) and Marketing Managers (7,5%).

- **Gender representation:** In terms of parity, the webinar recorded a total of 19 men (45,7%), 20 women (54.5%).

Besides, according to the users' survey completed by 4 participants, here are the satisfaction results:

- **Average satisfaction rate:** 70% of the respondents considered the webinars "Interesting" or "Of great interest".
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 50% of the respondents considered the webinars fitted their needs "Well" and 50% "Well enough".

7. Overall results and achievements

The combined results are as follows:

- **4 webinars** organized. One webinar was held for each pilot-region: Senegal, Kenya, Ghana, South Africa.
- Partners involved: **Bond'innov (Senegal), Hapa (Ghana), Wazi Up (Kenya), Methys and Enrich in Africa Center (South Africa).**
Association of African Universities and Steinbeis were also involved in supporting the organization of the webinars and ensuring their dissemination via a newsletter and social media posts.
- **1 419 registration page views**
- **473 registrations**
- **149 participants in total**, including:
 - Senegal: **36 participants**
 - Kenya: **39 participants**
 - Ghana: **35 participants**
 - South Africa: **39 participants**
- **The 4 webinars replays have been uploaded on SEADE Youtube channel:**
<https://www.youtube.com/@SEADEProject>

Main information regarding the participants:

Due to a bug in Teams concerning the export of data for the Kenya webinar, data from Kenya could not be included in the results below.

- **Geographical localization:**
69,1% came from African countries, 24,5% from European countries and 6,4% didn't fill the field or came from outside of Africa and Europe.
- **Country breakdown:** 20% of the participants came from South Africa, 19,1% from Ghana, 13,6% from France, 10,9% from Senegal. Participants from Kenya, Germany, Benin, Nigeria, Uganda, Spain, Egypt, Tunisia also joined the webinars.
- **Organization types:** More than 30% of the participants were from companies. Innovative startups/SMEs were also widely represented with 20% of the participants coming from a startup. Digital innovation hubs, Higher education institutes and private innovation support organizations representatives were an important proportion of the participants of the webinars.

- **Gender dimension:** 44,3% of the participants were women and 55,7% were men.

8. Users' survey feedback

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, the beneficiaries of the webinars have also reported the following results:

- **19 users' survey forms received**, including :
 - 52,6% from their participation to the Senegalese webinar
 - 21,1% from their participation to the South African webinar
 - 15,8% from the Kenyan webinar
 - 10,5% from the Ghanaian webinar
- **Average satisfaction rate:** 84,2% of the respondents considered the webinars "Interesting" or "Of great interest".
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 84,2% of the respondents considered the webinars fitted their needs "Well" or "Very well".
- **Country breakdown:** 29,4% of the respondents were from South Africa, 23,5% from Senegal, 11,8% from Kenya, 5,9% from Ghana, France, Burkina Faso, Belgium, Tunisia.
- **Organization types:** Among respondents, 21,1% were Innovative SME/Startups representatives, 15,8% Corporate representatives and 15,8% Policy Makers.
- **Gender representation:** 57,9% were men, 26,3% were women (15,8% didn't fill in the field).

D. Learning Expeditions

1. Overall presentation

The Learning Expeditions were designed and implemented by the 4 pilot regions leaders (BOND, HAPA, WAZI, MET). Each Learning Expedition was organized on-site in each of the four pilot regions during one week and targeted 10 participants each as the KPI.

The aim of these Learning Expeditions was to allow EU and SSA R&IID participants explore market opportunity, meet local stakeholders in order to understand the local context.

Enrolled participants took part in training courses, visits and meetings with key players, individual B2B appointments and national events to familiarize them with the R&I context and ecosystem of the pilot region concerned.

2. Deviations from workplan

Deviations are mentioned in the presentation of the activity concerned.

3. Senegalese Learning Expedition

As part of the partnership established between Bond'innov and Enabel, a Learning Expedition was organized in Belgium from May 12 to 16, 2025, for Ivorian players from the digital, research and innovation sectors. This initiative is part of both SEADE (Strengthening the Europe-Africa Digital Ecosystem) and PEM N'Zassa (Pilot for Entrepreneurial Mobility) projects. These initiatives respectively aim to strengthen links between African and European entrepreneurial, research and innovation ecosystems.

Co-organized by Bond'innov and Enabel, this Learning Expedition is based on a collaborative methodology combining : joint preparation of the program by Bond'innov, rigorous final selection of participants by Enabel and Bond'innov and a clear division of responsibilities between Bond'innov and Enabel.

- **Deviations from workplan**

Initially, the program had been designed to welcome 11 participants (in order to meet the 10 participants KPI), identified on the basis of criteria defined jointly with Enabel. The 11 participants confirmed their participation in the Learning Expedition. In the end, 6 Ivorian R&ID actors were able to take part in the mission. This reduction can be explained by several factors:

- One entrepreneur was rejected because he informed us at the last minute that he had a criminal record;
- Last-minute cancellations due to administrative constraints (visa delays);
- In some cases, logistical constraints managed by an Ivorian service provider (participants were informed the day before that the flight would take place the following day.)

Despite this change, the organizing team maintained the program as planned, adapting certain formats to encourage exchanges in smaller groups and provide more personalized support. This reduced format also facilitated greater proximity with the Belgian partners met, and enabled richer, more targeted interactions.

- **Timeline**

The preparation of the Learning Expedition was based on a collaborative, progressive and targeted approach, built around a shared desire between Bond'innov and Enabel to maximize the added value of the meetings for the Ivorian participants, while ensuring the relevance of the Belgian structures mobilized. The methodology involved several complementary phases :

- Identifying and qualifying Belgian partners: The Learning Expedition was not directly subject to a public call for applications but was already part of Enabel's selection process for its PEM N'Zassa program. Bond'innov and Enabel worked together on the participant final selection process, based on strategic exchanges aimed at ensuring the relevance of the profiles to the mission's objectives and to the two programs (SEADE and PEM N'Zassa). This rigorous, collaborative organization ensured the coherence of the group, while matching the profiles with the partnership opportunities identified in Belgium. This process led to the identification of a shortlist of 11 candidates. Unfortunately, no women were selected through the application selection process as their ventures weren't considered as innovative solutions.
- Program construction: The mission program was designed around a balance between collective(group) moments, individual meetings and time to discover local ecosystems.
- Taking participants' expectations into account: Prior to the mission, Bond'innov implemented different activities in order to gather participants' expectations, by way of: a group video call to present the program and collect individual priorities; a one-to-one call to better understand their specific needs; a structured questionnaire was sent out to identify the themes of interest, the types of partnerships sought, and specific needs.

● Learning Expedition implementation programme

The Learning Expedition program was designed to offer participants an immersive, progressive, and contextualized experience within the Belgian innovation ecosystem. Organized around collective meetings, thematic workshops and institutional visits, the program enabled participants to discover the wealth of innovation dynamics in Belgium, while identifying concrete opportunities for collaboration.

The program is presented below :

Le programme

	Matin / Midi	Après-midi
Lundi 12 Mai	Arrivée des participants en Belgique, check-in hôtel	13h45 Rencontre introductive à Enabel - Bruxelles
Mardi 13 Mai	9h00 Rencontre avec Fintech Belgium, pitches & réseautage - Bruxelles <i>Pour les opérateurs fintech uniquement</i> <i>L'association de référence qui fédère les acteurs de la fintech en Belgique et promeut l'innovation dans les services financiers.</i>	14h00 Visite de BeCentral - Bruxelles <i>Un hub dédié à l'innovation et à l'éducation numérique. Il héberge des startups, des formations en coding et des initiatives liées à l'IA et à la cybersécurité.</i>
	11h30 Rencontre à l'Ambassade de Côte d'Ivoire - Bruxelles	Déjeuner collectif à BeCentral (12h30 - 13h15)
Mercredi 14 Mai	11h00 Visite de Sirris - Liège <i>Le centre collectif de l'industrie technologique belge, qui accompagne les entreprises belges dans l'adoption des technologies avancées et l'innovation.</i>	14h00 Visite de La Grand Poste - Liège <i>Un hub créatif et entrepreneurial qui accueille startups, médias, espaces de coworking et activités culturelles dans un cadre rénové.</i>
		Déjeuner collectif à La Grand Poste (13h - 14h)
Jeudi 15 Mai	10h00 Visite de Wintercircus - Gand <i>Un écosystème innovant dédié aux industries créatives, aux technologies et à la collaboration intersectorielle.</i>	14h00 Temps libre dédié aux rencontres B2B
		Déjeuner collectif
Vendredi 16 Mai	9h30 Visite de The Beacon - Anvers <i>Un centre d'innovation technologique qui rassemble entreprises, startups et chercheurs autour des smart cities et de l'IoT.</i>	
		Midi / Après-midi Déjeuner de clôture, retour à Bruxelles et temps libre dédié aux RDV B2B

Funded by
the European Union

Table 1: Learning Expedition's programme

- **Results, achievements and best practices**

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Region distribution:** 100% of participants come from Côte d'Ivoire.
- **Gender distribution:** 100% of participants were men.
- **Age distribution:** The beneficiaries are young people, with an average age of 37.
- **Type of beneficiaries distribution:** The majority of respondents (67%) identified as Innovative SMEs, Startups, or Spinoffs, while 17% came from higher education institutions and another 17% from established companies.

The results are as follows:

- 15+ Belgian organizations visited, including innovation hubs, research centers, investors, technology companies, and incubators;
- 20+ professionals met, including public decision-makers, sector experts, and financing stakeholders.
- The Learning Expedition paved the way for several promising avenues of collaboration, which remain to be explored and consolidated in the coming months.
- **Nb. of countries covered by project activities (activity report) : 2**
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I : 4**
- **Nb. of new international collaboration : 12**
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers. : 0**
- **Nb. of financial partnership : 1**

- **Users' survey feedback**

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, Learning Expedition beneficiaries reported the following results (6/6 user survey forms received, representing 100% of participants):

- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 100% of the participants considered that the learning expedition program met their needs "very good" or "good".
- **Projects advancements:** 83% of the participants reported that the SEADE Learning Expedition helped them turn a project into reality. The remaining 17% indicated that it was still too early to assess the outcomes at this stage — a sign of promising dynamics still in progress.
- **Emerging outcomes and connections:** 50% of participants reported having already initiated a new international collaboration following the SEADE Learning Expedition. Other outcomes included the recruitment of an expert, active partnership discussions, and follow-ups pending responses from Belgian stakeholders — illustrating the tangible impact and forward momentum generated by the mission.

- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

The organization of this educational expedition provided an opportunity to test several methods and systems that proved particularly effective, while highlighting a number of points to monitor in

the future. This section summarizes the lessons learned at the operational level, both in terms of organization and strategy.

Best practices

- **Co-construction with a local partner (Enabel):** The fact that the project was designed and managed in close collaboration with Enabel was a key factor in its success. In particular, this collaboration enabled : an optimized division of responsibilities (Bond'innov on content, Enabel on logistics); efficient mobilization of resources (especially for mobility budget on the Enabel side); better mutual understanding of R&IID actors' expectations, constraints and work rhythms; invaluable local support (Enabel on site in Belgium) in case of emergency.
- **Structured upstream preparation:** Program quality was enhanced by : calls with participants to identify their expectations (questionnaire and/or introductory video); careful selection of the Belgian structures met, based on thematic compatibility and collaboration potential; virtual meetings organized with Belgian structures to explain the program and validate their participation.

Challenges encountered

- **Lack of control over logistics:** One of the major challenges of this edition was the delegation of logistics management to an external partner. While this facilitated certain tasks, such as reducing program costs, it also limited the reactivity to unforeseen events (delays, cancellations, schedule changes, etc.).
- **Final participation rate lower than expected:** Of the 11 participants initially selected, only 6 were ultimately able to take part in the Learning Expedition. This reduction in the number of participants was mainly due to visa-related constraints, in particular: long processing times that were incompatible with the planned schedule, the complexity and rigor of the supporting documents required which delayed the progress of certain procedures.

4. Kenyan Learning Expeditions

The learning expedition was the final stage of the 'Route to Market' program in Kenya as the learning expedition was part of the larger AIoT Route to Market program.

It was a **one-week** activity and took place between the 25st and the 29th of August 2025. The purpose of the learning expedition was to provide the innovators with an opportunity to physically inspect and engage the potential markets selected and linked to during the Soft-landing mission period. The participants were facilitated to travel and stay in Kenya for 5 days and explore the selected markets in Kenya.

A general workshop was set at the beginning of the activity at Konza Technopolis and included local experts that trained in the soft-landing mission and stakeholders from Konza Technopolis and KENInvest. The remaining days were gap analysis sessions/fact finding missions and involved visiting 4 of the selected industries to get insights on the level of service delivery improvement based on the solutions deployed. The same 5 groups in Tanzania and 2 groups in Kenya that participated in

the Softlanding mission program also took part in the landing expedition. A questionnaire was prepared and evaluated for circulation and feedback during the fact-finding missions at the industry levels.

- **Deviations from workplan**

No deviation from the workplan

- **Program Agenda**

The table below provides a summary of the learning expedition program:

Date	Time	Activity	Responsible
Day 1: 25th August 2025	9.00 - 9.30	Welcome Note (Waziup, AAU, DTBi Tanzania, Merseburg)	Joseph Shitote (Waziup), Isabella Tetteh Ahinakwa (AAU), Elias Kikota (DTBi), Nikita Fauke (Merseburg), Donald Odhiambo (Tectona Group)
	10.00 - 10.30	Presentation: Results of the Softlanding and Learning Expedition in Ghana	Isabella Tetteh Ahinakwa (AAU)
	9.30 - 10.00	Presentation: Introduction of the Learning Expedition and objectives	Joseph Shitote (Waziup)
	10.30 - 11.00	Break	
	11.00 - 11.30	Presentation: Research Landscape in Kenya	Konza Technopolis
	11.30 - 12.00	Presentation: Investment Landscape in Kenya	KenInvest
	12.00 - 13.00	Presentation: Industry take (Success story on industry integration)	ICIPE, Solargen, Ubuntu Hub, Tectona Group
	13.00 - 14.00	Lunch	
	14.00 - 17.00	Presentations: Success story of the matchmaking sessions in the Softlanding mission. [Industry	All participants

		integration of the solutions in Kenya markets]	
Day 2: 26th August 2025	9.00 - 13.00	Welcome to industry 1, Tour in the potential sites for integration. Natural break included	Joseph Shitote, Sheila Otuko, Brian Keya, Industry Representative
	13.00 - 14.00	Lunch	
	14.00 - 17.00	Workshop discussion: Assessment of industry 1 (Site analysis, potential design and test, value addition, suitable solution integrations)	All Participants
Day 3: 27th August 2025	9.00 - 13.00	Welcome to industry 2, Tour in the potential sites for integration. Natural break included	Joseph Shitote, Sheila Otuko, Brian Keya, Industry Representative
	13.00 - 14.00	Lunch	
	14.00 - 17.00	Workshop discussion: Assessment of industry 1 (Site analysis, potential design and test, value addition, suitable solution integrations)	All Participants
Day 4: 28th August 2025	9.00 - 13.00	Welcome to industry 3, Tour in the potential sites for integration. Natural break included	Joseph Shitote, Sheila Otuko, Brian Keya, Industry Representative
	13.00 - 14.00	Lunch	
	14.00 - 18.00	Key site tours (networking dinner)	Joseph Shitote, Sheila Otuko, Brian Keya
Day 5: 29th August	9.00 - 12.00	Workshop discussion: Review of solutions in	All participants

2025		groups and preparation of the next steps	
	12.00 - 12.30	Introduction to Enrich in Africa and the Resources available for Startups.	EnrichinAfrica - Melanie Mwangi
	12.30 -13.00	Presentations: Review of solutions, learnings from sites, challenges, next steps.	All participants
	13.00 - 14.00	Lunch	
	14.00 - 17.00	Presentations: Review of solutions, learnings from sites, challenges, next steps.	All participants
	17.00 - 17.30	Closing Remarks	Joseph Shitote (Waziup), Isabella Tetteh Ahinakwa (AAU), Elias Kikota (DTBi), Nikita Fauke (Merseburg)

Table 2: Learning Expedition program

The Innovators had an opportunity to provide a status update of their engagement with the markets selected during the soft landing mission. This then escalated to an evaluation session with the markets involved for an understanding of the level of integration of the solution and the gap filled following the solution deployment. A summary workshop was held as the final item to gather feedback and develop a report.

● **Results, achievements and best practices**

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Gender Representation:** Participant gender representation with nearly 1/3 of the participants identifying as female
- **Age Representation:** Participant age representation with more than 80% of the participants being between the age of 18-25.
- **Organisation Type:** Participant organisation representation with more than 80% of the participants coming from Innovative SME/Startup/Spinoff and Digital Innovation Hubs.
- **Country Representation: Kenya (41.6), Tanzania (41.6), Germany (16.6).** The reason for the low number of European participants was due to a limitation of budget to support their travel to the Kenyan markets. This number was limited at the beginning of the program to fit within the program budget.

At the end of the program which ended with the learning expedition, the results are as follow:

- 24 innovators were trained from Kenya, Tanzania and Germany

- 11 market partners were engaged for suitable matching with the innovators all of which developed plans for future engagement and scaling.
 - 7 of the 11 groups that transitioned from the Softlanding managed to meet with their market matches physically in Kenya.
 - **Nb. of countries covered by project activities (activity report):** 3 (Kenya, Tanzania, Germany)
 - **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 11 (1 per team of innovator)
 - **Nb. of new international collaboration:** 6 (Tanzania, 5, Germany, 1)
 - **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers:** 8 (Trainers invited for each course in the softlanding)
 - **Nb. of financial partnership:** 0 (No financial partnerships formed)
- **Users' survey feedback**

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, Learning Expedition beneficiaries reported the following results:

- **Meeting needs and Expectations:** 54,5% of the participants agreed that the program met their needs and expectations “very well”.
 - **Innovation Progress:** 100% of the participants agreed that the learning expedition helped improve their innovations “significantly”.
 - **Quality of Industry Match:** More than 90% of the participants agreed that they were matched to a relevant industry during the learning expedition.
 - **Confidence in Market Transitioning:** More than 90% of participants (90,9%) had more confidence in transitioning their innovations to the Kenyan market at the end of the program.
- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

Upskilling innovators with digital and business skills for solution development aids in the development of quality solutions that are easily absorbed in a specific market. Enabling innovators to meet the market stakeholders physically helps to strengthen the chances for solution up-take by the respective markets and scaling. The European ecosystem provides many opportunities for their innovators which leads to many of them preferring to concentrate on the European side and not Africa. Publicity is necessary to showcase opportunities available in Africa to encourage most Europeans to transition their solutions in Africa.

5. Ghanaian Learning Expeditions

The SEADE Ghana Learning Expedition was organized by Hapa Space and the Association of African Universities (AAU). This event brought together innovators, researchers, and policymakers from across Africa and beyond, representing countries such as South Africa, Uganda, Kenya, Botswana, Mayotte, Senegal, and Ghana. This learning expedition ran parallel to two significant events: the ASENTI (Africa Summit on Entrepreneurship and Innovation) and the Ghana Digital Innovation Week (GDIW). Both events provided valuable insights into the Ghanaian innovation ecosystem and offered participants an opportunity to engage with industry leaders and policymakers through panel discussions. A key highlight of the expedition was the SEADE booth at GDIW, which provided

participants with the opportunity to showcase their products and interact with the local and international community. The booth also served as a platform to share information on the SEADE project, fostering connections and promoting the project's objectives.

- **Deviations from the workplan**

No specific deviation from the workplan.

- **Timeline**

Launch of the project: 1st August 2024

Call for Application: 1st August 2024 - 20th September 2024

Selection of Participants: 23rd September 2024

Notice of Participation: 24th-26th September 2024

Learning Expedition: 30th September to 6th October 2024.

The 7-days event was full of experiential learning and opportunities to strengthen the EU-AU collaboration in the R&IID space.

- **Call for applications:** The call for applications opened from 1st August 2024 to 20th September 2024 to allow Hapa to recruit the right people for the LEX. Fortunately, HAPA has the opportunity to collaborate with GDIW 24 (organised by GIZ, Ghana Hubs Network, Impact Investing Ghana and National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programme) and ASSENTI Africa. This collaboration alone exemplified the AU EU collaboration.
- **Selection of the participants:** The participants were selected based on their interest and their ability to participate in the event physically in Ghana. The majority of the participants were already attending the ASSENTI and GIDW 24. This was helpful since we did not have enough budget to convey people from other countries and accommodate them in Ghana for the 7 days.

Beyond the main participants, the different activities attracted other participants due to the partnership with the 2 conferences, GDIW 24 and ASSENTI. Overall, the SEADE Ghana Learning Expedition engaged approximately 174+ participants across various activities, including panel discussions, networking sessions, and ecosystem tours.

- **Learning Expedition programme**

The programme was fully packed with activities from the GDIW 24, ASSENTI conference and other ecosystem activities. Find the detailed activities schedule below.

Date	Detail	Location	Responsibility
30.09.2024	Kickoff meeting	Accra	Gideon Brefo + GDIW Team
01.10.2024	African Summit on Entrepreneurship and Innovation (ASENTI)	Kofi Annan ICT Center	Dr. Jones Opoku-Ware Gideon Brefo Philipina Appiah

	8.30 am-4 pm Networking Dinner (10 Africans+EU; Int. Partners + GDIW organizers) 5.30-9pm	Association of African Universities (AAU)	Naomi Kokuro Hapa & AAU Team
02.10.2024	GDIW: Exhibition + Networking 9:00 am-5:00 pm	AICC	Hapa & AAU Team
03.10.2024	GDIW: Exhibition + Networking Panel Discussion: <i>Enhancing Digital Transformation: Collaborative Research and Innovation between Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa</i> 2:30 pm-3:30 pm	AICC	Hapa & AAU Team Panelists: Gideon Brefo 6. Evelyn Kwarteng 7. Dr. Jones Opoku-Ware 8. Abena Konadu Baidoo 9. Jefferson Seneadz
04.10.2024	GDIW: Exhibition + Networking	AICC	Hapa & AAU Team
05.10.2024	Ecosystem Tour	Academic City Relu Technologies	Hapa & AAU Team
06.10.2024	B2B Meetings: Scheduled meetings for the 10 European and African innovators, researchers, and policymakers	AAU/AICC/Virtual	Dr. John Serbe Marfo Dr. Jones Opoku-Ware Gideon Brefo

Table 3: Ghanaian Learning Expedition agenda

- **Results, achievements and best practices**

Number of participants: 13 participants

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Avg. satisfaction rate (user’s survey):** 90%
- **Rate of participation in activities per region, per gender, per age and per type of beneficiaries (user’s survey):** Gender: Male 7, Female 6; Researchers 2; Entrepreneurs 11

The results are as follows:

- **Nb. of countries covered by project activities (activity report): 9**
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I: 4**
- **Nb. of new international collaboration: 4**
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers.. : 0**
- **Nb. of financial partnership: 0**

- **Users' survey feedback**

As part of the SEADE Ghana Learning Expedition, feedback was collected from participants to evaluate their experiences, networking success, and overall satisfaction with the event. A total of 8 responses were gathered, providing insights into key areas of success and areas for improvement.

Participant Demographics:

- **Countries of Residence:** Participants came from a diverse set of countries, including Kenya, Uganda, South Africa, Botswana, Cameroon, Mayotte, Guinea, and Ghana.
- **Gender:** 75% of participants were male, while 25% were female. Despite the rigorous campaign, fewer females applied. The HAPA team did its best to contain all ladies that applied.
- **Age Group:** The majority of participants (62.5%) were between 26-35 years old, with smaller percentages in the 18-25 (12.5%) and 36-45 (25%) age groups
- **Roles of participants:** Participants held various roles including lecturers (12,5%), researchers (12,5%), innovators (12,5%), entrepreneurs (12,5)s, business consultants (12,5%) and university staff (12,5%). This diversity in professional backgrounds contributed to the rich discussions throughout the event.

Satisfaction feedback:

- **Global satisfaction rate:** 100% of participants indicated a strong commitment to maintain the corporation began with Ghana and even requested they get connected with other softlanders in other regions.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 100% participants answered that the service was “of great interest” to them.
- **Needs fitted:** Out of eight respondents, five indicated that the service fitted their needs “very well”, two said “well”, and one felt it was “well enough”.
- **Projects advancements:** 8 participants reported that the SEADE Learning Expedition helped them turn a project into reality.
- **Emerging outcomes and connections:** 8 participants reported having initiated new collaboration in R&D, 2 participants reported having already initiated a new international collaboration following the SEADE Learning Expedition. Other outcomes included sales at an exhibition.

Some participants suggested improving clarity in linking the various connected events (ASENTI and GDIW) to the SEADE program ahead of time, which would enhance understanding and preparation.

- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

- **Collaboration Opportunities:** The visit to Relu Interactive created space for discussions on potential collaborations between SEADE and Relu Interactive. Both entities share a common goal of advancing digital education and making it more accessible to all. Participants explored ideas for joint initiatives, including research collaborations and partnerships aimed at scaling EdTech solutions across the African continent.
- **Reflections and Learning Outcomes:** The Ecosystem Tour provided a hands-on experience that highlighted how VR, AR, and other digital tools are revolutionizing education. The day's visits reinforced the importance of collaborative innovation in addressing the educational challenges facing the African continent, with a clear focus on how technology can provide scalable solutions for the future.
- **Networking and Connections:** The tour allowed participants to engage with faculty members, innovators, and other stakeholders, sparking conversations about joint ventures, research partnerships, and the potential for expanding EdTech solutions beyond Ghana. Participants left the day energized and inspired by the opportunities for cross-border collaborations in the EdTech space.
- **Future Interests:** Participants expressed keen interest in entering the Ghanaian market as researchers, innovators, and entrepreneurs. Several provided their contact details to explore further collaboration opportunities, especially when SEADE's Soft Landing Program begins.

6. South African Learning Expedition

The SEADE South African Learning Expedition, organized by Methys, took place from the 27th of November to the 5th of December 2024.

The South African program brought together innovators, researchers, and policymakers from across Europe and Africa, representing the following countries: Zimbabwe, Kenya, France, Spain.

A key highlight of the program was that participants were provided opportunities to be speakers at the Innovation stage during the AfricArena Grand Summit in which they could talk about their business, organization or institution. They also got to engage with SEADE Summit speakers and interact with the local and international community that attended the SEADE Summit on the 4th of December.

- **Deviations from the workplan**

Below is the change and deviation:

- **Number of participants:** Methys experienced a number of dropouts from its selected 10 applications during the 2nd week before the program started due to decline of visas, visa applications being longer than 2 weeks and the expense of flights during peak season in

Cape Town.

Thus, Methys could only get 9 committed participants of which 3 came from outside the application process and 1 out of those 3 could only attend the learning expedition on the last 3 days of the program.

The final number of participants that participated in the full program was 8 with the 9th participant arriving on the 3rd last day of the 8 day program

- **Timeline**

The SEADE South African Learning Expedition timeline consists of the following:

- May 2024 - Learning Expedition conceptual planning
 - Suggested dates the 19 of April 2025 to the 26th of April 2025
 - Locations Johannesburg and Cape Town
- June 2024 - Change in dates of Learning Expedition program to 25th of November 2024 to 1st of December 2024 and waited on approval
- August 2024 - Approval of date changes
- September 2024 - Learning Expedition Program design and reach out for speakers and host in Johannesburg and Cape
- 27 September - Learning Expedition locations change from Johannesburg and Cape Town to just Cape Town due to the lack of resources to cover both cities at the same time as other programs in Cape Town
- 4th of October - Call out for applications to the Learning Expedition published online and across networks
- 25th of October - Applications close
- 28th October - Top candidates shortlisted for discovery call interviews
- 29th October to 4th of November - Shortlisted candidates discovery calls
- 8th November - Top 10 candidates announced to participate in the Learning Expedition
- 11th November - Program Orientation and logistics
- 18th November - Final logistical meeting on pending visas and flights to South Africa
- 27th November - Program starts

- **Call for applications:** The Call for Applications to join the South African Learning Expedition were published online and across Methys and SEADE networks on the 4th of October 2024. The call for applications was advertised on the SEADE website and social media channels. The call for applications was also marketed across Methys social media channels as well as on the French South African Tech Labs website.

- **Selection of the participants:** Methys received 21 applications for the SEADE South African Learning Expedition, following an extension of the call due to low initial response. Ten applicants were shortlisted and interviewed through discovery calls to assess their profiles and commitment, leading to a final selection announced on 8 November. The selected participants received an online orientation on 11 November covering program details and logistics. After several withdrawals by 15 November, additional applicants were contacted, resulting in three confirmed replacements, while others declined participation.

- **Learning Expedition implementation programme**

The South African learning expedition program consisted of a series of visits to innovation centres, universities, think-tanks, investor firms and co-working spaces within Cape Town on the 27th, 28th and 29th of November. The expedition program during these days also featured 3 networking events where the program participants could network with other peers in the ecosystem. These events were the following:

- **AESIS Networking Cocktail Evening** - Angel investment mixer on the 27th of November
- **UCT GSB Pitch Day** - 20 research and innovation startups from across Africa pitched at UCT to students, lecturers, investors and ecosystem players on the 28th of November
- **GIZ Togo Demo Day** - Scaling and Investing in Francophone Africa where 12 Togolese startups pitch to ecosystem players and investors on the 29th November

During the weekend of the 30th and the 1st of December, the group split into two groups consisting of the startups and innovation centres going to a dealflow bootcamp at Monkey Valley Beach Resort for the 1st and 2nd of December and participants who chose to rest during the weekend and meet leads from the first 3 days. The deal flow bootcamp hosted 10 speakers from the Cape Town ecosystem that provided workshops on design thinking and innovation, investment fundraising, cloud computing, pitching and networking during the two days. The boot camp also offered networking opportunities where participants were provided interactions with 40 other tech and digital entrepreneurs from across Africa.

The South African learning expedition program also ran in parallel with two events during the week of the 2nd to 6th of December. The two events associated with the learning expedition in which participants attended were the AfricArena Grand Summit from the 3rd to the 4th of December and the SEADE Summit on the 4th of December 2024. Both events provided valuable insights into the South African and African innovation ecosystems and offered participants an opportunity to engage with industry leaders, policymakers, startups and innovation centres through a range of panel discussions, networking events and pitch challenges.

Below the highlights of the program:

- 1st December - AfricArise Bootcamp
- 3rd December - AfricArena Grand Summit with Innovation Stage
- 4th December - AfricArena Grand Summit and SEADE Summit
- 5th December - Departure back to home countries
- 9th December - Program Feedback Surveys Send
- 12th December - Group Online Reflection Workshop

- **Results, achievements and best practices**

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Nb of participants:** 9 participants
- **Region distribution:** 3 from Europe (France, Spain), 6 from Sub- sahara Africa (Kenya, Zimbabwe)
- **Gender distribution:** 62,7% were men, 37,5% were women

- **Age distribution:** 50% were between 25 and 30 years old, 25% between 30 and 35 years old, 25% above 35 years old.
- **Type of beneficiaries distribution:** 25% from Higher Education Institutions, 25% from Incubators related to academia or research center, 25% from Digital Innovation Hubs.

SEADE's South African Learning Expedition was a success even though there were some glitches along the way with missed flights, blocked visas, and accommodation. Here are some results:

- **Nb. of countries covered by project activities:** 4 (France, Zimbabwe, Spain, and Kenya)
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 1
- **Nb. of new international collaboration:** 67 agreements of collaboration
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers:** 1
- **Nb. of financial partnership:** 0
- A total of 15 engagements with R&I ecosystem players were made and facilitated by Methys during the Cape Town tour.
- From the 5 events attended, an average of 6 collaborative engagements were made by each of the LEX participants.
- 80% of participants found the learning expedition of Cape Town provided by Methys as a quality service in providing a tour of the R&I ecosystem in Cape Town and linking them to potential collaborative ecosystem players
- 50% of the participants stated that they had secured future engagements and negotiations on collaborative partnerships with ecosystem players they were introduced to by Methys or meet at the 5 events

- **Users' survey feedback**

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, Learning Expedition beneficiaries reported the following results:

- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 75% of the respondents considered the service was "interesting", 12,5% "of great interest", 12,5% "so-so".
- **Needs fitted:** 62,5% considered the service fitted their needs "well enough" and 37,5% "well".
- **Projects advancements:** 75% of the participants reported that the SEADE Learning Expedition helped them turn a project into reality.

- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

Best practices

From the experiences Methys obtained during the SEADE South African Learning Expedition of Cape Town, South Africa in the later part of 2024, Methys has identified a number of best practices that future Learning Expeditions can consider. These best practices consist of the following:

- **Online Connector Conferences Before Program:** Methys was successful in conducting online masterscalls and connectors before Learning Expedition participants travelled to Cape Town. These online connector conferences consisted of: One onboarding and program conference with selected LEX participants ; One on one discovery calls ; Online mixers with

potential lead connections before the program ; A State of Innovation in South Africa workshop to provide insight to selected participants on where opportunities lay in the innovation sector in South Africa

- **Connector Tours:** Methys had great success in conducting its connector tours with a specific framework that provided innovation hosts with an opportunity to promote themselves and the LEX participants the opportunity to engage the innovation hosts one on one.
- **Securing Events for Participants to Attend:** Methys was successful in providing the SEADE Learning Expedition participants with as much exposure and networking as possible through a series of events organised by Methys and partners. The SEADE LEX participants were able to attend 5 events during their stay in Cape Town.

Challenges

Methys experienced a number of challenges during the SEADE South African Learning Expedition. These challenges include the following:

- **Confined period between call of applications and start of program:** The initial planning by MET was too optimistic in the number of applications it would receive over 4 weeks as well as the onboarding period of the participants after the announcement of the selected. Methys had not given itself enough time to process the applications and manage logistics which had effects in the later stages of confirming selected participants and getting them to South Africa. To assure this does not happen again it is recommended that the call for applications is done 4 months before the program and 10 weeks are given to manage logistics of securing visas, accommodation and flights.
- **Visas:** South Africa has some strict visa processes for certain West African countries as well as a few European countries. The South African embassy and government often denies visas to Nigerian nationals and we have had 1 denial. While the visa application process for Nigeria nationals takes 4 weeks to process, thus the selection of participants need to be 8 weeks before the program to give Nigeria and other West African nationals to apply and be granted their visas. Other countries from Europe that also have a 2 week to 4 week processing time are countries from Eastern Europe like Romania and Luxembourg.
- **Flights:** Methys had a couple of drop outs due to the expense of flights to Cape Town during the peak season, thus it is recommended going forward that future learning expeditions are hosted outside the South African peak season or one allows selected participants with a 2 month leverage so they can book cheaper flights.
- **Hotel Bookings:** Due to Peak Season in Cape Town with an estimated 25 000 tourists booked into hotels across the city of Cape Town during the week from the 27th of November to the 5th of December, it was extremely difficult to secure rooms within the allocated budget and thus the LEX participants were moved another of times to different hotels during the course of the week which negatively affected the program. For future LEX programs to Cape Town, it is recommended that one runs learning expedition programs out of season especially during the November and December periods as most of the City of Cape Town is booked out during November and December due to graduating matrics, tourists, ocean liner tourists, and investors and startups during Investor Week. During the LEX week, a total of 7000 tourists went to shore for the week from 3 ocean liners which caused hotel booking problems for Methys. Methys will consider hosting Learning

Expeditions in March and April and October and November respectively going forward. Methys only hosted the Learning Expedition at the end of November and beginning of December so participants could be involved in the I&R Summit and AfricArena Summit on the 3rd and 4th of December.

C. Softlanding Programmes

1. Overall presentation

The Softlanding programmes were designed and implemented by the 4 pilot regions leaders (BOND, HAPA, WAZI, MET). Each Softlanding programme was organized remotely (with the possibility for the participants to travel to the site at their own expense) in each of the four pilot regions during 3 months and targeted 10 participants each as the KPI.

The aim of these Softlanding programmes was to support EU and SSA R&IID participants to prepare and succeed their implementation in a pilot region country and/or support them in developing collaborations with R&IID actors in Senegal.

Enrolled participants took part in training courses, workshops, feedback sessions from R&IID actors, virtual visits of key actors and meetings (online or in real life) with key players, individual B2B appointments to build strong collaborations with R&IID actors.

2. Deviations from workplan

The overall softlanding program experienced the following deviations;

- The participants' mobility was not a prerequisite for their participation. Indeed, the limited budget did not allow them to subsidize their mobility, and the long duration of the program (3 months) limited the possibilities for participants to carry out such a long mobility. The activity would take place online, with the possibility for participants with the means to travel to the pilot country for 2 weeks. The pilot region leader concerned would welcome participants on the move.
- Participants from both Europe and Sub Sahara Africa are accepted as long as the pilot leaders do their best to include European participants as much as possible.

These deviations were submitted to the European Union Project Officer, who validated this proposal for all SEADE softlanding programs.

3. Senegalese Softlanding

The Senegalese soft-landing program was designed and delivered by Bond'innov in Year 1, targeting 10 selected research & innovation actors from Subsahara Africa and Europe to support the setting up of partnerships between European and/or sub-Saharan African and Senegalese players, and/or to support the establishment of these players in Senegal, with the ultimate aim of supporting their mobility.

The laureates enrolled in the program participated in training, workshops and various meetings to strengthen their knowledge of the Senegalese ecosystem and its players, to structure a search for partnerships and initiate or confirm partnerships with Senegalese players.

During the 3-month program, the innovators got to discover the Senegalese research & innovation ecosystem, while being supported by Bond'innov's team who facilitated the match-making process.

- **Specific deviations from the workplan**

No specific deviations from the workplan other than those listed above.

- **Timeline**

The Senegalese soft-landing program, including its preparation, started in April 2024 and ended in December 2024. The timeline of the program can be divided in 7 main steps:

- **Preparation of the soft-landing framework** (April-June 2024)
- **Call for applications conception** (May-June 2024)
- **Call for applications launch and extension** (July-August 2024)
- **Pre-selection and final selection of 10 R&IID actors** (August-September 2024)
- **Kick-off** (September 17 2024)
- **Implementation of the soft-landing program** (September-December 2024)
- **Users' survey feedback and activity report** (December 2024)

- **Call for applications:** Before releasing the call for application, several preparatory activities were implemented: Design of the framework of the softlanding program activities, conception of the softlanding action plan, Design of the call for application general strategy (planning, communication strategy and relaying partners, visuals, ...), Preparation of the landing page containing the program description and its promise to the participants, Design of the terms and conditions of the call for projects, Preparation of the application form and templates to collect candidates information, Preparation of eligibility and selection criteria. The dissemination channels used to promote the call for application were the following : Bond'innov's channels (posts on the LinkedIn page), SEADE's channels (newsletter, landing page, posts on the LinkedIn page, promoted posts), Enrich in Africa Center platform, Bond'innov's partners channels.

To maximize the participation of European players, Bond'innov reimbursed the mobility expenses (up to a maximum of €3,000 for a maximum of 15 days) of the two best European applications. This opportunity was publicized through Bond'innov channels.

Following the launch of the call for applications on the platforms listed and communication actions supervised by WP6 Leader (Steinbeis), 43 applications were received, 37 applications were eligible (9 from Europe / 28 from Africa).

- **Selection of the participants:** Activities for this stage of the program consisted of designing the whole selection process and timeline. The process was divided into 2 consecutive parts : Eligibility screening of applications and Evaluation and selection of the 10 laureates. Based on the eligibility criteria, the 43 applications were filtered by Bond’innov team to keep only the eligible candidates (37). Then, a selection among the 37 eligible candidates was conducted by Bond’innov. On the basis of eligibility and evaluation, the 10 best applications were selected to take part in the program.

- **Softlanding programme**

The preparation of the structure, calendar and content of the Senegalese soft-landing program, started a few months before the program. The program had the following components where internal preparation was required ahead of time:

- Program of the activities (adapted and refined)
- Mobilization of Senegalese key actors
- Collection of participants’ needs and expectations
- Identification and organization of the collective workshops topics to fit participants’ needs and expectations
- Conception of the welcome booklet
- Preparation of the kick-off meeting
- Creation of the Whatsapp group
- Preparation of the kick-off meeting

The softlanding program was composed of 4 main steps:

1. **Kick-off (Weeks 1 & 2):** The first two weeks were onboarding weeks, starting with the program kick-off on September 17th 2024. Outside the kick-off meeting, the following activities were carried out during the first two weeks: Filling in participants' needs forms ; Organizing the first calls to diagnose the participants' collaborative projects, based on the pre-completed forms ; A Pitch & Connect session where each participant introduced himself/herself and his/her project, to create cohesion within the group and identify potential avenues for collaboration within the participants themselves. It was organized September 24th.
2. **Diagnosis and partnership hunting (Weeks 3 & 4):** The main goal of this step was to get to know the participants and the challenges they were facing but also their goals and support them with training courses.
3. **Get to know the environment (Weeks 5 to 7):** The main goal of this step was to allow them to get to understand the Senegalese ecosystem and cultural and professional habits better to be ready to get in touch with potential partners.
4. **Matchmaking (Weeks 8 to 12):** The main goal of this step was to support them to identify and get in touch with relevant Senegalese actors.

Throughout the program, Bond'innov also organized follow up meetings to monitor participants' progress towards their objectives and to help them make connections with Senegalese players.

The activities implemented are the following:

- **Individual follow up calls:** The first individual calls with the 10 participants occurred between October 03 2024 and October 11 2024. 10 calls were organized. The second individual calls with the 10 participants occurred between November 11 2024 and November 15 2024. 10 calls were organized. The main goal of these follow up calls was to take stock of the consolidation of their collaboration project, identify difficulties and provide advice, identify networking needs and validate next steps. Indeed, the Bond'innov's referents acted as coaches, with whom the innovators could discuss the progress of their prospect activities, based on the roadmap previously established together. The final individual calls with the 10 participants occurred between November 24 2024 and December 7 2024. 10 calls were organized. These calls represented an opportunity to take stock of their progress in terms of partnerships, agree on points of attention for the next stage of their project, and share the latest tips and updates.
- **Training and workshops:** The following training courses and/or workshops were delivered to participants throughout the program (either by Bond'innov or by external experts):
 - Presentation of the Senegalese R&IID ecosystem (October 9th)
 - Developing a partnership: best practices (October 15, 2024)
 - Intercultural management: keys to meeting the challenges (October 21, 2024)
 - Canva Connexion: how to identify the right partners (October 29, 2024)
 - Collaboration and prospecting in Senegal: best practices and feedback (November 6, 2024)
 - Preparing your presence in Senegal: What you need to know! (November 12, 2024)
 - Developing your business in Senegal: In-depth analysis of best practices and levers for success (November 19, 2024)
 - Prospecting in Senegal: Best practices and feedback (November 28, 2024)
 - Discovering the Sen start-up association (December 03, 2024)
 - Advice on financing structures, focus on Senegal (December 10, 2024)
 - ⇒ A total of 21 contacts were made and facilitated by Bond'innov as part of individual coachings.
 - ⇒ 7 meetings between participants and actors from the Senegalese ecosystem were successfully completed during the Softlanding programme.
 - ⇒ 5 follow-up meetings were scheduled and carried out during the Softlanding program. A total of 50 follow-up meetings for the 10 participants.
- **Program closing:** An online closing event was organized on December 17th. It provided an opportunity to review the activities carried out as part of the program through key indicators, to analyze in detail the elements of the satisfaction questionnaire and to enable participants to share their feedback. The session also enabled the Bond'innov team to offer advice and share best practices to support participants as they continue their adventure in Senegal.

The users' survey was also shared with the participants.

- **Results and achievements**

Number of participants: 10 participants involved during the 3 months.

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Region distribution:** Participants represent a diverse range of countries, reflecting the international scope of the program and its success in attracting interest from several regions. 50% come from Europe and 50% from West Africa.
- **Gender distribution:** 70% of participants in the SEADE softlanding program in Senegal are men, compared with 30% of women.
- **Ages of participants:** The average age of the participants was 40.6 years
- **Type of beneficiaries distribution:** The program has attracted a wide range of profiles, with SMEs and higher education institutions leading the way at 30% of participants.
- **Position held:** All participants held management or decision-making positions. This indicates the program's ability to attract high-level professionals, in line with its objective of fostering high-impact partnerships.
- **Sector of activity:** Participants were active in various sectors that place innovation at the heart of their structures.

The results are as follows:

- 2 collaborations are currently being set up between two participants in the Softlanding program and two identified Senegalese partners:
- 2 implementation of European organizations in Senegal:
 - One has started the registration procedure to set up in Senegal.
 - One plans to open a branch in Dakar.
- **Nb. of countries covered by project activities (activity report):** 5
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 0
- **Nb. of new international collaboration:** 2
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers.. :** 0
- **Nb. of financial partnership:** 1

- **Users' survey feedback**

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, the beneficiaries of the webinars have also reported the following results (9 users' survey forms received, including 44,4% from European participants and 55,6% from Subsahara Africa participants):

- **Average satisfaction rate:** 89% of participants found the service they received "interesting" and "very interesting", which testifies to the quality of the service.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 66% of the participants considered that the softlanding programme met their needs "perfectly" or "very good".
- **Projects advancements:** 66% of participants answered that the program has helped them to turn their project into reality or that it is under negotiation/in progress. 56% detailed this goal achieved or in progress as "a new international collaboration"

In addition to the satisfaction questionnaire, participants expressed their satisfaction via various channels.

- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

During the implementation of our program, Bond'innov encountered various challenges that required adjustments and innovative solutions. By identifying and implementing best practices, Bond'innov was able to overcome these obstacles and enhance the participants' experience.

Challenges encountered

During the implementation of the program, several structural and organizational challenges were identified.

- Firstly, a disparity in participant involvement was observed, with a notable difference between the mobilization and commitment of African and European laureates, particularly in terms of participation in the sessions and activities proposed.
- Secondly, adapting to a 100% online format over a three-month period posed challenges in terms of maintaining participants' motivation in a virtual environment, requiring regular adjustments to ensure their commitment.
- In addition, availability and time constraints, such as jet lag and participants' busy schedules, made it difficult to synchronize group sessions.
- Finally, as the end-of-year period (September - December) is a busy time for companies, team closure proved limited.

Best practices

To overcome these challenges and ensure an enriching experience for participants, several best practices were put in place:

- The use of dynamic and interactive formats, such as participative workshops and question-and-answer sessions, improved the quality of training sessions.
- Personalized follow-up was also introduced to maintain the commitment of participants, particularly those facing specific obstacles.
- In addition, clear and regular communication, with systematic and constant reminders, helped to maintain momentum throughout the program.
- Scheduling the majority of workshops on a single date (i.e. each Tuesday at the same time slot) helped to create a group culture within this short-term program.
- Last but not least, the involvement of experts from different fields provided participants with highly enriching perspectives on their projects.

4. Kenyan Softlanding

- **Program Overview and Requirements with Timeline**

The SoftLanding mission was the second stage of the Route to Market program with the function of enabling the innovators access the markets in Kenya. It took place for 3 months from 12th of May

to the 1st of August 2025 with two key stages: Product preparation and Market engagement. Training sessions were organized to guide the innovators on business skills and support them during the market engagement sessions. The program involved 5 groups of 2 each (10 participants) in Tanzania, 5 groups of 2 each (10 participants) in Kenya and 2 groups of 2 each in Europe (4 participants). In total there were 24 participants in the program from Tanzania, Kenya and Europe. The groups were already working on an IoT solution and had interests in scaling the solution to the Kenyan Market. The learning model was primarily virtual with dedicated sessions where the participants engaged and learned from each other.

The best performing groups were selected for the Learning expedition.

● **Deviations from workplan**

For the softlanding in Kenya, we report the following deviation from the general plan of execution of activities in all the pilot regions. To increase the potential of the number of Europeans and other SSA countries connecting to the pilot regions, it was generally agreed to involve only Europeans and SSA participants outside of the pilot region in the activities. Since the Kenyan activities were connected, and the Digital Youth Training Programme already involved 10 Kenyans, it was decided that they continue the Softlanding and the Learning Expedition activities to maintain their learning and validation of the program. 10 Kenyans joined the 4 Europeans and 10 Tanzanians in the Softlanding program. The participation of the Kenyans did not affect the overall KPI of this activity.

● **Program Agenda**

The summarized Agenda was given by the table below with 4 weeks dedicated to solution preparation and the remaining 8 weeks for Industry Matching.

Month	Week	Theme	Description
April	Week 1	Solution Preparation and Industry Pitching	Presentation and Understanding (Introductory webinar) - 2hrs Product design and life cycle - 2hrs
	Week 2		Solutions Market analysis
May	Week 3	Industry Matching and Engagement	Introduction of the Kenyan Markets (Stakeholders)
	Week 4		Alignment and Pitching to the Kenyan Markets
	Week 5		Solution Alignment to selected Industry/Market Needs
	Week 6		
June	Week 7	Industry Matching and Engagement	Solution Redesign to match Industry needs
	Week 8		Solution deployment/testing in the market
	Week 9		
	Week 10		

Jul	Week 11		
	Week 12		Feedback Assessment and Reporting

Table 4: The Softlanding mission program structure

External experts were invited to conduct some of the sessions such as those on funding opportunities, business registration, Intellectual property and business policies. Experts prepared their training materials and presented them to the innovators.

● Execution

The Softlanding mission kicked off with an introductory session where the participants from Kenya, Tanzania and Europe were taken through the general structure of the program and the expectations. The participants also had a chance to make presentations on their innovations. The participating teams were chosen across various fields such as agriculture, water and sanitation, clean energy, smart homes, wildlife and vehicle monitoring.

The softlanding mission sessions were conducted weekly covering various aspects that would help the innovators navigate their route to market strategies. Industry experts were invited to take the innovators through these sessions.

The topics covered are shown in the diagram below. To facilitate these sessions experts from the Kenya National Innovation Agency (KeNIA), Jacob’s Ladder Africa (JLA), Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IEEE), Kenya Industrial Property Institute (KIPI), Law Society of Kenya (LSK) and Startinev were invited.

Figure 1: Soft Landing Mission Training Areas

Week 1 training was Product Design Life Cycle where the innovators were taught the various stages that a product goes through before it reaches the market. The sessions also covered the design thinking process of product development to ensure that the participants are building products that solve real world problems. The second session was on presentation and pitching. The facilitator taught the participants how to actively pitch and present their solutions to judges, investors and customers. Session three on Intellectual Property management helped the participants to understand the importance of protecting their innovation before commercialisation. The fourth session was focused on negotiation skills for innovators, a critical skill especially when dealing with investors. The fifth session introduced the innovators to legal matters that they should be aware of. The session covered basics such as business registration in terms of sole proprietorship, partnership and limited companies. The final session was on sales and marketing with the

participants being taken through various marketing strategies, steps in building a strong brand and the sales process.

After the business training sessions, the innovators were matched to industry experts in their field to whom they pitched their ideas and received feedback on better marketing strategies, business models and product positioning and development.

The soft landing mission successfully concluded with a closing ceremony where the participants shared their feedback and future plans for their innovations. A few industry experts were also invited to the session to offer guidance to the participants in their next steps. At the end of the ceremony, the learning expedition set to happen in Kenya was officially launched.

- **Results and achievements**

Number of participants: 24 participants

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Region distribution:** Kenya (10), Tanzania (10), Germany (4)
- **Gender distribution:** Participant gender representation with nearly $\frac{1}{3}$ of the participants identifying as female. As we used the same participants from the Digital Youth Training program and in all our follow up activities, the number of female participation was already affected by financial and road infrastructure difficulties accessing the venue. 4 women dropped out of the program on the second day. The planning team substituted them with an alternative batch of innovators from the waiting list to attend the program.
- **Ages of participants:** Participant Age representation with more than 90% of the participants aged between 18-25
- **Type of beneficiaries distribution:** Participant organisational representation with more than 80% of the participants coming from Innovative SME/Startup/Spin off and Digital Innovation Hubs.

The results are as follows:

- **Nb. of countries covered by project activities (activity report):** 3 (Kenya, Tanzania, Germany)
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 11 (for each group linked to the market)
- **Nb. of new international collaboration:** 7 (5 for Tanzania and 1 for Germany)
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers...:** 8 experts identified to support business training
- **Nb. of financial partnership:** None

One of the most significant achievements of the SoftLanding mission was the way participating teams were able to refine and align their AIoT solutions to real-world industry demands in Kenya. Through structured training sessions, industry introductions, and direct pitching opportunities, innovators moved beyond theory and began shaping their products around practical use cases. By engaging with stakeholders from sectors such as agriculture, water, energy, smart homes, and transport, teams gained an in-depth understanding of the Kenyan market landscape. This enabled them to identify gaps, refine their value propositions, and adapt technical features to industry-specific challenges. During pitching sessions, industry partners provided actionable

insights on product usability, scalability, compliance, and customer adoption. This feedback helped innovators improve their prototypes, redesign features, and prioritize functionalities that create the most impact. The mission also opened doors for long-term collaborations. Several innovators established early connections with potential partners, setting the stage for piloting and testing their solutions in real-world environments.

- **Users' survey feedback:**

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, the beneficiaries of the webinars have also reported the following results:

- **Average Satisfaction Rate:** More than 70% of the participants found the softlanding very well fitted to their needs as innovators
- **Innovation Progress as a result of the Soft Landing Mission Program:** More than 80% of the participants experienced significant improvements on their innovations
- **Industry Linkages:** 100% of the participants agreed that they had been matched to a relevant industry
- **Participant Confidence in Transitioning solution to market:** More than 80% of the participants felt confident in transitioning their solutions to the market after completion of the program.

- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

Inconsistent engagement with some participants showing fluctuating levels of attendance and commitment during the weekly sessions. To address this, the program introduced a variety of expert speakers each week, which helped refresh the learning experience and sustain participant interest throughout the 12 weeks.

Continuous improvement needs by ensuring that sessions met the diverse expectations of participants required ongoing adjustments. To mitigate this, post-session surveys were administered to gather real-time feedback. Insights from these surveys were incorporated into subsequent sessions, allowing the program team to continuously improve delivery and tailor content to participant needs.

5. Ghanaian Softlanding

The Softlanding Program in Ghana was designed to facilitate the entry of European and African innovators into the Ghanaian R&I ecosystem by providing essential resources, mentorship, and expert guidance. By bridging geographical and cultural divides, the Softlanding program aimed to ease market entry and foster lasting collaborations in research and innovation.

The specific activities undertaken in Ghana included:

- **Tailored Matchmaking:** Connecting softlanders with Ghanaian universities, incubators, investors, and corporations based on their specific research and business needs. This included introductions to key institutions like the West Africa Genetics Medicine Center at the University of Ghana and Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology.

- **One-on-One Mentorship and Sessions:** Facilitating direct engagements between innovators and local experts.
- **Capacity-Building Workshops:** Providing structured guidance and training sessions, such as the sessions on grant writing and research development for participants from the Ministry of Education in Ethiopia.
- **Practical Engagement and Knowledge Exchange:** Offering hands-on experiences and networking opportunities to provide firsthand insights into the Ghanaian market. This included a participant's engagement with local farmers and mentorship in the dairy sector.

- **Specific deviations from the workplan**

No specific deviations from the workplan.

- **Timeline**

The program's planning and preparation involved a series of strategic meetings to ensure a smooth and effective process. This started with a virtual kickoff on May 21, 2025, to introduce participants to the program and the ENRICH in Africa platform, a digital tool designed for cross-continental networking. The team also organized one-on-one sessions and coordination meetings with groups, such as the Malawi team, to understand specific needs and tailor the support provided. These efforts laid the groundwork for the core activities, including workshops and direct matchmaking with Ghanaian universities and businesses, ensuring a productive engagement for all involved.

The program's activities extended from April to July 2025 and were designed to provide practical, hands-on support.

- **May 21, 2025:** A virtual kickoff meeting was held for all participants from Europe and Africa. The session introduced the Ghana stream, set expectations, and planned for one-on-one matchmaking.
- **May 29, 2025 - August 30, 2025:** A one-on-one sessions for all Softlanders with their various stakeholders and experts
- **August 4, 2025 - August 24, 2025:** Participant came to Ghana, connected with stakeholders and conducted interviews with support from Hapa Space and the AAU team.
- **August 19, 2025:** The SEADE Softlanding Program officially concluded with a closing ceremony that brought together 23 participants, including softlanders, partners, and team members, to celebrate achievements and reflect on lessons learned.

The project's success was celebrated in a closing ceremony, which marked not just the end of the program but the beginning of sustained collaborations.

- **Call for applications:** The Softlanding program's preparation and planning involved a series of strategic activities to ensure a smooth and effective process for innovators entering the Ghanaian R&I market. The Hapa and AAU team designed a comprehensive framework that covered everything from a detailed action plan to a clear communication strategy for the call for applications.

Several preparatory activities have been implemented: Design of the framework of the softlanding program activities, conception of the softlanding action plan, Design of the call for application general strategy (planning, communication strategy and relaying partners, visuals, ...), Preparation of the landing page containing the program description and its promise to the participants, Design of the terms and conditions of the call for projects, Preparation of the application form and templates to collect candidates information, Preparation of eligibility and selection criteria.

- **Selection of the participants:** The selection phase for the program was a two-part process with a carefully designed timeline. First, all applications underwent an eligibility screening to ensure they met the program's core requirements. Following this, the eligible candidates were then moved to the second part of the process, the evaluation and selection of the 10 laureates.

Based on these criteria, the Hapa team carefully filtered the 39 applications received, identifying 29 candidates who were eligible to move forward in the selection process.

Then, a selection among the 29 eligible candidates was conducted by Hapa. On the basis of eligibility and evaluation, the 10 best applications were selected to take part in the program. An allowance was made for two more participants to join the Ghana softlanding activity. So the final selection came to 12 people.

- **Softlanding programme**

The Ghanaian soft-landing program's structure, calendar, and content were meticulously prepared in the months leading up to its launch. This required a great deal of internal preparation to ensure all components were ready.

The program was built on the following key components:

- The program's activity schedule was adapted and refined to fit its goals.
 - Ghanaian key actors were mobilized to ensure their active participation.
 - The SEADE team gathered participants' specific needs and expectations.
 - Collective workshops were identified and organized around topics that aligned with what participants needed and expected.
 - All materials and logistics for the kickoff meeting were prepared in advance.
 - A dedicated WhatsApp group was created to facilitate quick and easy communication.
- **Kick-off (Weeks 1 & 2):** The first two weeks of the program served as an **onboarding** period, beginning with the virtual kickoff on May 21, 2025, at 1:00 PM GMT. After participants were onboarded, the team conducted a **needs assessment** to understand each participant's specific requirements for entering the Ghanaian R&I ecosystem. Individual calls were scheduled with the participants to gather these insights. The information collected from these calls guided the selection and engagement of key stakeholders and experts who could provide **tailored support** to the AU-EU innovators interested in the Ghanaian R&I sector.
 - **Needs Analysis and Expert Hunting (Weeks 3-4):** The activities during weeks 3 and 4 were crucial for translating the program's general goals into actionable, customized support for

each softlander. This phase, focused on needs analysis and expert matching, commenced immediately after the initial two-week onboarding period.

The Hapa and AAU teams initiated a series of individual calls with participants to conduct a deep-dive needs assessment. The purpose was to pinpoint each innovator's specific requirements for successfully entering the Ghanaian Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem.

The precise insights gathered during this phase guided the expert hunting and matching process. The SEADE team strategically engaged key Ghanaian stakeholders and experts who possessed the exact expertise, facilities, or networks required by the softlanders. This tailored approach ensured that the connections made were maximized for relevant and effective collaboration.

- **Expert Meetings and Mentorship:** During this phase, participants engaged in a series of targeted one-on-one sessions and collaborative meetings with their matched experts and mentors. These meetings were the core of the softlanding process, designed to provide innovators with tailored guidance and support. This direct mentorship was crucial for helping participants refine their projects and adapt their business models to the local context.
- **Engagement with Governmental Institutions and Local Businesses:** The program also facilitated important connections with governmental bodies and local businesses to help innovators navigate the market. These engagements were vital for helping participants gain firsthand insights and build the networks needed to successfully enter the Ghanaian market.
- **Closing Ceremony:** The SEADE Softlanding Program concluded with a vibrant closing ceremony, bringing together participants, partners, and team members to celebrate the achievements and reflect on the lessons learned. The event was attended by 23 participants, including 12 softlanders and 3 partners.

The ceremony served as a platform for softlanders to share their experiences and for partners to offer their insights. The ceremony concluded with a keynote address from Charlie Guerin of Bond'innov, who encouraged participants to sustain their collaborations for long-term impact. Philipina Beatrice Brefo appreciated the joint efforts of all stakeholders, and Gideon Brefo reassured participants of ongoing support from HapaSpace and the AAU to help them nurture their connections. The closing ceremony marked not only the end of the program but also the beginning of lasting relationships and collaborations that will continue to drive innovation between Africa and Europe.

● Results and achievements

The Ghanaian Softlanding Program demonstrated tangible success across all key performance indicators, achieving high satisfaction rates, fostering significant cross-continental collaboration, and creating lasting partnerships.

- **Number of Participants:** 12 softlanders from diverse backgrounds engaged in the core activities, including tailored matchmaking and collective workshops.

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Region distribution:** The program successfully attracted participants from both European countries (Ireland, France, Cyprus, Luxembourg) and African countries (Nigeria, Ethiopia, Malawi).
- **Gender distribution:** Participant gender representation with nearly $\frac{1}{3}$ of the participants identifying as female.
- **Ages of participants:** Participant Age representation with more than 90% of the participants aged between 18-25
- **Sector coverage:** Diverse mix of perspectives across priority sectors like **HealthTech, Agroecology, Animal Production, and Digital Transformation.**

The results are as follows:

- **Nb. of Countries Covered by Project Activities:** 6 (Ethiopia, Nigeria, Malawi, Ireland, France, Cyprus, Luxembourg).
- **Nb. of New International Collaboration:** 6
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 4
- **Nb. of recruitments of experts, researchers:** 0
- **Nb. of financial partnerships:** 0. While direct financial investments were not finalized during the program period, the foundation for future partnerships was laid.

- **Users' survey feedback**

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, the beneficiaries of the webinars have also reported the following results:

- **Average Satisfaction Rate:** 8 out of 12 softlanders rated their experience as "**Satisfied**" or "**Very Satisfied.**"
- **Team Support:** 11 out of 12 participants found the SEADE/HapaSpace team to be "**Supportive**" or "**Very Supportive.**"
- **Program Effectiveness:** The majority of participants (9 out of 12) rated the program as "**Effective**" or "**Very Effective**" in helping them achieve their objectives.

The most valuable part of the program, as highlighted by many, was the opportunity for direct, tailored connections and access to local expertise. The team's reactivity and responsiveness were also praised as a key factor in the program's success.

Many participants felt the program successfully enhanced their skills and provided new opportunities. While the feedback was overwhelmingly positive, a few participants noted challenges, such as the limitations of a virtual-only program, which can limit the ability to build stronger human connections. However, the willingness of some participants to invest in future in-person trips demonstrates the program's effectiveness in building a foundation for continued collaboration.

- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

Reflecting on the program's execution, participant feedback, and key outcomes allows for the identification of successful best practices and areas where future softlanding initiatives can be strengthened.

Best Practices Identified

The program's high success rate and participant satisfaction were driven by core strategies focused on personalization and local immersion:

- **Tailored Matchmaking for High-Impact Collaboration:** The most critical success factor was moving beyond generic introductions to facilitate highly specific pairings. By conducting a detailed needs analysis, the team successfully matched innovators with counterparts possessing exact expertise, institutional facilities, or market access.
- **Prioritizing Hands-on and In-Person Engagement:** While the program was predominantly virtual, the instances where physical immersion occurred proved most impactful.
- **Responsive Team Support and Coordination:** The Hapa and AAU teams were consistently praised for their rapid response and dedication, acting as a reliable bridge between the innovators and the Ghanaian ecosystem.
- **Leveraging Institutional and Partner Networks:** The program effectively integrated high-profile partners. This network provided credibility and essential, often difficult-to-access, information necessary for foreign market entry.

Challenges Met and Lessons Learned

Several structural and logistical challenges were identified, offering important lessons for subsequent programs:

- **Limitations of Virtual-Only Softlanding:** A recurring theme was the difficulty in sustaining momentum and building deep, trusting relationships solely through virtual means.
- **Sustaining Partner Commitment Post-Introduction:** While initial matchmaking was excellent, some participants reported that the engagement from their paired partners or mentors waned after the initial session. This suggests a need to implement structured follow-up mechanisms or a framework to ensure partners are "fully and sincerely committed" to the collaboration for the duration of the program.
- **Clarity on Financial and Funding Opportunities:** The process for identifying and clarifying funding opportunities needs improvement. One softlander noted, "Funding opportunities were not communicated clearly," creating uncertainty about next steps for market scaling.
- **Addressing Financial Constraints for Academic Exchange:** The ambition for deeper academic exchange was hindered by the financial constraint of local host institutions being unable to cover travel and associated expenses. Future programs should explore mechanisms, such as designated mobility reimbursement funds (similar to practices in other SEADE streams), to ensure that the initial successful academic match can be realized on the ground.

6. South African Softlanding

The SEADE South African Programme, organized by Methys, took place from the 08th of November to the 28th of December 2025. The South African program brought together innovators, researchers, and policymakers from across Europe and Africa, representing the following countries: Mozambique, Nigeria, Cameroon, France, Lithuania.

The South African soft-landing program consisted of a series of online workshops, webinars, one on one engagements and a learning expedition in Cape Town. The online program consisted of 8 workshop webinars with guest speakers and one on one connectors with aligned sector based leads.

These online workshop webinars and connectors included the following:

- Introductory and onboarding workshop
- The State of Innovation in South Africa Webinar
- The Enrich in Africa Centre Connector and Webinar on the EIA platform
- The State of Digital Research in South Africa webinar hosted by Propella (Nelson Mandela Bay University)
- Cape Town Ecosystem Reflective Workshop
- The State of Tech in Africa Webinar hosted by AfricArena
- Digital Regulation in South Africa hosted by Laywered Up
- The City of Cape Town - Your Digital Gateway hosted by the Department of Economic Development and Tourism
- Going to Market in South Africa webinar hosted by Sw&
- Soft-landing Closing and Reflection workshop

The on the ground soft-landing expedition program consisted of a 14 day tour of Cape Town's innovation and research ecosystem and a series of networking events including the R&I SEADE Summit and the AfricArena Grand Summit. Soft-landers visited innovation centres, universities, think-tanks, investor firms, innovation hubs and co-working spaces within Cape Town from the 22nd of November to the 6th of December 2024.

At these centres, universities, think-tanks, investors firms and co-working spaces participants were provided with tours of the spaces, presentations and panel discussions provided by the hosts on research and innovation within their work, operations, projects and spaces. The on-the-ground soft-landing program of Cape Town also included a number of networking events for the soft-landers to attend where they could network with other peers in the ecosystem.

During the weekend of the 30th and the 1st of December, the group was split into three groups consisting of the startups, innovation experts and venture capital investors that attend 3 different multi day round table events across Cape Town. For participating startups, they attended an innovation dealflow bootcamp at Monkey Valley Beach Resort from the 1st to 3rd of December. For the innovation experts they either joined the founder's dealflow bootcamp as speakers or they toured the city during the weekend. For participating VC investors and selected innovation experts, they attended the Digital Collective Africa's VC Unconference in Franschhoek.

Soft-landing participants also participated at two large innovation summits during the program in Cape Town, the AfricArena Grand Summit from the 3rd to the 4th of December and the SEADE Summit on the 4th of December 2024. The involvement of participants in the two events included participants being placed as speakers in panel discussions or getting the opportunity to pitch their business or organization. Both events provided valuable insights into the South African and African innovation ecosystems and offered participants an opportunity to engage with industry leaders, policymakers, startups and innovation centres through a range of panel discussions, networking events and pitch challenges.

After the in person and on the ground soft-landing in Cape Town, the program continued in the new year of 2025 where a series of online workshop connectors were scheduled between digital research and innovation specialists, organizations, institutions and investors and the soft-landing participants. Additional one on one coaching sessions for each participant were conducted to assist participants in understanding the different digital and innovation markets of South Africa and connecting them with role players aligned to their specific needs.

- **Specific deviations from the workplan**

The work plan for the South African pilot region soft-landing went through a number of changes and deviations since the M6 of the SEADE Project. Below are the changes and deviations:

- Number of participants - Methys experienced a number of dropouts from its selected 10 applications at the start of the program due to lack of time to attend the online workshops and the resources to attend the in person and on the ground soft-landing in Cape Town. Thus, Methys experienced a number of changes to the original selected participants while only 60% of participants were able to make the soft-landing tour program in Cape Town.
 - The final number of participants that participated in the soft-landing tour of Cape program was 6
- The online program was extended into March as there were some connector workshops that had to be rescheduled as guest speakers could make certain dates.

- **Timeline**

The SEADE South African Soft-landing timeline consisted of the following:

- May 2024 - Soft-landing conceptual planning
 - Suggested dates the 8th of November 2024 to the 14th of February 2025
 - Location: Online and Cape Town
- July 2024 - Approval of soft-landing dates and program
- August 2024 - Soft-landing program design and reach out for speakers and Cape Town tour hosts
- September 2024 - Soft-landing content and call for applications adverts designed
- 15th of September - Call out for applications for the South African soft-landing program published on SEADE website, social media accounts, online and across networks
- 15th of October - Applications closed
- 18th October - Top candidates shortlisted for discovery call interviews

- 20nd October to 4th of November - Shortlisted candidates discovery calls
 - 25th October - Top 10 candidates selected
 - 30th October Top 10 participants announced to participate in the Soft-landing program
 - 4th November - One on One meetings with each participant on their needs and goals for the program
 - From 8th November - Program onboarding, introduction and program connector workshop
 - 14th of February - Soft-landing Program Reflection and Feedback
 - 15th of February - The end of the soft-landing program
- **Call for applications:** The Call for Applications to join the South African Learning Expedition were published online and across Methys and SEADE networks on the 4th of October 2024. The call for applications was advertised on the SEADE website and social media channels. The call for applications was also marketed across Methys social media channels as well as on the French South African Tech Labs website.

From the call for applications, Methys received a total of 35 applications by the 25th of October 2024. Most applications can be from Methys weekly newsletters where the call for applications was advertised once a week for 4 weeks. There was also a considerable effort by the Methys team in their marketing of the call for applications in mailers and communication with ESO partners in Europe and Africa as well as universities.

- **Selection of the participants:** Methys received a total of 35 applications for the SEADE South African Soft-landing program Expedition by the 25th of October. Interviews with the applicants were then scheduled from the 28th of October to the 1st of November in which applicants were asked a series of questions and why they want to be on the soft-landing program. During this week participants were scored on their application and interview and final results submitted to the selection committee of Methys on the 1st of October. The 10 applicants were announced by email on the 4th of November while the other non selected applicants were sent emails of thanks for their applications on the same day.

From the 35 applicants, 10 applications were shortlisted. Once the top 10 applicants were shortlisted in selection, one conducted discovery call interviews with them on their shortlisting with the objective of understanding them more, their work and their ability to commit to the program. Discovery calls were conducted from the 28th of October to the 4th of November. The final selection was decided on the 4th of November and announced publicly on the 8th of November.

- **Specific deviations from the workplan**

METHYS experienced a number of dropouts from its selected 10 applications within the 3rd week of its program.

- a. Of the 10 selected and engaged only 8 came to the online workshops after the program orientation and onboarding on weeks 2 and 3. By week 3 of the program, 2

selected participants stated that they did not have time for the program and dropped out.

- b. In the same week, 3 other selected participants stated that they would not be able to join the soft-landing tour of Cape Town on the 24th of November due to not having budget for the high holiday season flight ticket and their visas either being declined or not having enough time to secure a visa to South Africa in terms of the required processing period.
- c. Thus on the 3rd week of November, Methys had to go through the remainder of the applicants to see who could come to Cape Town as we only had 5 selected participants who were committed to coming to Cape Town. None of the non selected applications could make it at such short notice.

At the beginning of the 4th week of the program, 4 days before the start of the Cape Town tour, another selected participant of the remaining 5 pulled out of the program due to logistical worries about the program in Cape Town.

With only 4 participants confirmed for the Cape Town tour, Methys looked outside of the applicants to research and innovation ecosystem players that did not have to require applying for a visa, had the funding to secure a flight to Cape Town and were motivated to secure partnerships in South Africa through the program.

By the 20th of November we had secured an additional 4 participants to attend the soft-landing Cape Town tour.

A total of 7 committed soft-landing participants made it to Cape Town on the 24th of Cape Town and participated in the tour program while 3 selected applicants remained at home and will only participate in the program online during 2025.

Thus Methys has 10 soft-landing participants, 7 of whom took part in the tour of Cape Town and have been part of the online webinars and 3 that have just been part of the online webinars and one on one support.

- **Softlanding Programme**

- **Week 1: Soft-landing Orientation Workshop and one on one meetings:** Week 1 of the SEADE South African Soft-landing program was an 1 hour and half orientation workshop with the selected program cohort on the 3 month program. The workshop also included a networking session, individual feedback on hopes and aspirations of the program and breakout rooms on South Africa's market. One on one meetings with each participant was also diarized for the next month.
Meetings with each soft-landing participant was then conducted during the week in which Methys conducted partner and client hit list exercises with each participant, planned their logistics to Cape Town for the on the ground soft-landing and outlined the objectives and goals of each participant during the program.
- **Week 2: The State of Innovation in South Africa:** Week 2 of the SEADE South African Soft-landing program was on the State of Digital Innovation in South Africa in which Methys held a 2 hour workshop on the digital economy of South Africa and what opportunities that

the participants could take in the economy. Participants were also provided an exercise to conduct in mapping their own opportunities in the digital and innovation economy of South Africa.

During the week of the 11th of November, there were also one on one meetings with each participant on the logistics of getting to Cape Town on the 25th of November for the ground program and who they wanted to connect to in terms of potential partners, clients or investors.

- **Week 3: Enrich in Africa Centre and Platforms Engaging partners:** In week 3 of the SEADE South African Soft-landing program, the cohort was introduced to the Enrich in Africa Centre and how the Centre and its online platform assists digital innovation champions in Europe and Africa connecting and working with each other and how the participants of the cohort could use the online platform in fostering partnerships and finding opportunities between the two continents. Each of the participants of the program was then taken through an exercise of registering to the EiA platform and creating their profile on the site. Participants were also introduced to other African and European channels for engagement in research and innovation online.

During the week of the 18th, each participant of the cohort went through their hit list of potential clients, partners, investors and innovators they would like to connect to during the program and while in Cape Town. Match making and a connection road map was drafted for each participant and introductory emails sent to targeted South Africa digital research and innovation role players.

- **Week 4: The Ground Soft-landing - Cape Town:** In week 4 of the SEADE South African Soft-landing program, 7 participants from the cohort flew into Cape Town on the 24th of November and were booked in the Cape Town City Lodge for the beginning of the soft-landing's ground program.

- **Results, achievements and best practices**

Here are some brief highlights and stats of the 8 day Learning Expedition in Cape Town:

- **Number of Participants:** 10 participants part of the program online (4 from Europe, 6 from Sub- sahara Africa) / 7 participants (3 from Europe, 4 from Sub- sahara Africa) toured Cape Town.

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Region distribution:** 25% from France/Luxembourg, 25% from Ivory Coast, 25% from Senegal, 25% from Tanzania.
- **Sector coverage:** 50% Innovative SME, 25% Corporate, 25% Research institutions

The results are as follows:

- **Nb. of Countries Covered by Project Activities:** 8 (Nigeria, Mozambique, France, Luxemburg, Cameroon, Senegal, Tanzania, Kenya).
- **Nb. of New International Collaboration:** 5

- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 1
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers:** 1
- **Nb. of financial partnership:** 0

- **Users' survey feedback**

The South African Softlanding program was a success across key performance indicators, achieving good results in collaboration and satisfaction among participants which highlighted the impact of the cross-continental program.

- **Number of Participants:** 10 participants from Europe and Africa consisting of 2 European and 8 African participants
- **Gender distribution:** 80% male and 20% female
- **Ages of participants:** Participant age representation consisted of participants with the age bracket of 30 to 50.
- **Average Satisfaction Rate:** 6 out of 8 South African softlanders that completed the survey rated their experience as "**Satisfied**".
- **Team Support:** 6 out of 8 South African softlanders that completed the survey found the Methys team to be "Supportive".
- **Program Effectiveness:** 7 out of 8 South African softlanders that completed the survey 7 rated the program as "Effective" in supporting collaboration between South African and their organization.

Most responses by participants highlighted the ground Soft-landing in Cape over 2 weeks as a valuable part of the program that assisted them with direct access to opportunities in the city and tailored connections with local expertise.

Other feedback from the respondents of the survey was the need for more in-person soft-landing connections than online, however, they did state the online masterclasses on innovation in South Africa were great and that some of the online connections were good in being introduced to local South African experts in digital innovation and research that they could engage in t

- **Best practices identified and challenges met**

Reflecting on the program's execution with participants after the ground soft-landing program in Cape Town and at the end of the program in January, the best practices for future programs were identified and some of the challenges that the participants experience that Methys will need to work on. These best practices and challenges are the following:

Best Practices Identified

The South African soft-landing program's success rate and participant satisfaction were driven by core strategies of local in person interactions and personal focus for custom needs of collaboration and partnership:

- **Tailored Online Matchmaking for Collaborations:** At the start of the program, Methys conducted needs assessments with each participant and then afterwards conducted target partnership sampling of experts in South Africa associated with the field of research and

innovation that the participant was in. From these exercises, Methys was able to match each participant online with targeted experts to foster opportunities of collaboration and partnerships. By conducting a detailed needs analysis, the team successfully matched innovators with counterparts possessing exact expertise, institutional facilities, or market access.

- **On The Ground and In-Person Engagement:** While the program was virtual over 6 weeks, the highlight for participants was the on the ground soft-landing for 2 weeks in Cape Town where they were able to meet their targeted potential partners in person to seal agreements or MoU or collaborations. Participants also mentioned that matching the program with a large event such as the AfricArena Grand Summit and the SEADE Research and Innovation Summit was highly beneficial and impactful as they will be able to pitch their innovations, research and businesses at the two events and get to meet a range of people outside of their targeted partners. For future programs it was suggested to run more in person and hands-on activity in pilot regions like South Africa. Participants suggested they would have liked to have visited Johannesburg as well.
- **Leveraging Venture Capital and ESO Partner Networks:** Methys was able to effectively integrate high-profile venture capital investors for the businesses involved in the program from its network which was highly appreciated by the participants. Through partnering ESOs in South Africa, participants were able to attend multiple events during their 2 week program in Cape Town while also expanding their reach to potential partners through the networks of Methys ESO partners.

Challenges Met and Lessons Learned

The challenges experienced by participants and Methys that were identified during two reflective meetings that offered important lessons for future programs are the following:

- **Limitations of Virtual Program:** Feedback from participants suggested that the virtual program of the soft-landing could be shortened as they experienced difficulty in sustaining momentum and relationships solely through virtual means. Feedback suggested that 4 weeks of virtual program before the ground program worked well, but one could shorten the virtual program to 2 weeks to 4 weeks after the pilot site visit.
- **Match Makings Commitments:** Participants found virtual match making and partnership building difficult to sustain and get commitment from the counterparts. However, participants did state that the method of introductions virtually and partnership engagements in person while visiting the pilot site worked well in securing meaningful collaborations. Participants who were not part of the on site pilot program in Cape Town struggled with committed working relationships to build a partnership.
- **Visas:** One Nigerian ESO participant was denied a visa to South Africa for the ground landing in Cape Town even with a selection letter and time to spare. South Africa has some strict visa processes for certain West African countries as well as a few European countries. Processing time for some European and African countries is 4 weeks, thus for future programs, one must consider a 8 week period for visa entry logistics of participants.
- **Flights:** Methys had a couple of drop outs due to the expense of flights to Cape Town during the peak season, thus it is recommended going forward that future ground programs are conducted outside peak season in Cape Town and Johannesburg.

D. Bootcamp training programme

1. Overall presentation and timeline

The role of the bootcamp was to bring together EU and SSA actors to upskill their capacity to bridge the gap between research and market success.

The themes of the 5 bootcamp sessions were identified and validated on the basis of the results and lessons learned from the Work Packages 1 and 2 studies thanks to an internal workshop held on January 24th, 2025.

The bootcamp sessions were held in English as it wasn't possible to ensure live translations (cf. already tested for the webinars). 40 participants were expected to meet the initial KPIs.

The 5 bootcamp sessions are listed below:

1. Navigating Challenges that limit market access for R&IID Innovations in Europe and Africa
2. Funding Pathways and Practical Strategies for Research & Innovation Actors
3. Strategies for Youth and Women Empowerment in Digital R&I
4. A Playbook for Research and Innovation Investment: How to Engage Investors and Raise Investment
5. How-to Connect and Develop a Successful Collaboration between EU-SSA Actors

The first two sessions occurred on April 24, 2025 and the three last sessions occurred on September 18, 2025.

A communications plan was launched between March and April 2025 to promote the April webinars via the SEADE LinkedIn page and the project website. Each of the pilot regions also communicated about this activity to their respective communities.

At the end of each bootcamp session, each host sent the users' survey form in order to gather feedback from participants, in accordance with Work Package 5 (Deliverable 5.1).

2. Deviations from workplan

No deviations from the workplan.

3. Navigating Challenges that limit market access for R&IID Innovations in Europe and Africa

The first bootcamp session took place on April 24, 2025 from 08 am GMT to 10am GMT. This session was titled 'Navigating Challenges that limit market access for R&IID Innovations in Europe and Africa' and focussed on providing a picture of the digital research market in Europe and Africa. This involved providing an understanding of the current situation and the challenges that exist in this market ecosystem. It was meant for innovators with digital solutions and were interested in testing and applying them in either of the continents and were facing challenges.

This bootcamp was an opportunity for them to learn the market dynamics, evaluate their approach and learn from success stories demonstrated in the bootcamp. Case studies from both Kenya and Cyprus were provided. These case studies were strong in the sense that both were

co-developed by European and African partners to achieve success. The Kenyan Case Study showcased successful implementations of IoT Agricultural deployments in Benin and Nigeria and an innovative learning platform ‘The Wazilab platform’ as a tool for rapid training of emerging technologies. The Cyprus case study showcased successful digital products in Health, Energy and Water through their Gravity Ventures incubator.

Speaker Name	Partner Organization	Expertise	Topic	Duration (CET)
Joseph Shitote	Waziup	Program Manager	Introduction to SEADE, Waziup, and the Wazilab Case Study	10.00 - 10.30
Moyseos Moyseos	EBN, Gravity Ventures, CyRIC EUBIC	Incubator Manager	A mapping of the market situation in Europe and Africa and their challenges	10.30 - 11.30
Brian Keya	Waziup	Training Expert	IoT Agricultural deployments in Benin and Nigeria: A case Study	11.30 - 11.45
Q & A	All Participants			11.45 - 12.00

Table 5: Session program

The importance of this bootcamp session to the participants can be presented in three main parts:

6. Getting the correct picture of a particular market ecosystem
7. Addressing cultural and social barriers as a challenge for market penetration
8. Simply finding reliable contacts in a given target market destination

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** a total of 25 participants during the session.
- **Average satisfaction rate:** 100% of respondents considered this session as “of great interest”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 75% of respondents considered this session met their needs and expectations “well” and “very well”.

4. Funding Pathways and Practical Strategies for Research & Innovation Actors

This bootcamp session took place on April 24, 2025 from 10 am GMT to 12am GMT. The session was designed to equip research and innovation (R&I) actors with the knowledge, strategies, and tools needed to secure sustainable funding. It brought together leading experts, industry stakeholders, academia, and R&I practitioners from Maseno University from Kenya, EuroQuity, Steinbeis, Bond’innov and Association of African Universities.

The session covered:

- EU-Africa strategic partnerships and joint initiatives (e.g., Horizon Europe, African Union–EU High Level Policy Dialogues).
- Horizon Europe structure: Pillars 1 (Excellent Science), 2 (Global Challenges), 3 (Innovation Europe).
- Examples of ongoing Africa-Europe collaborative projects.
- Eligibility and pathways for African researchers (e.g., Marie Curie, EDCTP, collaborative projects).
- How to find calls and partners (via the EU Funding & Tenders Portal and networking events).
- Step-by-step guide for accessing funding (from identifying calls to writing proposals).

The outcomes for the audience were to:

- Gain a comprehensive understanding of how EU funding is structured.
- Learn how African institutions can engage, register, and benefit.
- Receive tips and tools (e.g., partner portals, PIC registration) for applying.

By the end of the bootcamp, participants walked away equipped with:

- A clear roadmap for accessing and applying to Horizon Europe and other EU funding opportunities.
- Practical insights drawn from real-world case studies such as SEADE, PrAectiCe, and Living Labs.
- Strategic awareness on how to future-proof their funding approaches through diversification, commercialization of research, and engagement with policy frameworks.
- Valuable tools and upcoming opportunities to expand their networks, including information on the SEADE R&I Summit in Spain and EU mobility schemes.

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** 63 participants to this session.
- **Countries representation:** 7,4% from Spain, 3,7% from Belgium, 3,7% from Germany, 7,4% from France, 7,4% from Nigeria, 14,8% from Somalia, 11,1% from Kenya, 11,1% from South Africa, ...
- **Gender representation:** 80% were men, 20% were women
- **Average satisfaction rate:** 83,33% of respondents considered the session of “great interest” and 16,67% “interesting”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 66,67% of respondents considered the session met their needs and expectations “very well” and 33,33% “well”.

5. Strategies for Youth and Women Empowerment in Digital R&I

The virtual bootcamp under the theme Strategies for Youth and Women Empowerment in Digital R&I was organized by the Association of African Universities in collaboration with the Enrich in Africa Centre (EiAC).

This event was anchored on findings from SEADE’s needs assessment across its four pilot regions, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, and Senegal, which revealed persistent challenges that limit the inclusion of women and youth in digital R&I, including traditional gender roles, limited mentorship, and inadequate access to funding opportunities. Hence, it aimed at strengthening inclusivity in the

digital research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem by equipping underrepresented groups, particularly women and youth, with knowledge, skills, and opportunities to effectively participate.

The bootcamp was designed to:

- Equip participants with practical knowledge on accessing and navigating the digital R&I ecosystem.
- Foster inclusivity by addressing barriers to women and youth participation.
- Raise awareness of emerging opportunities in digital R&I spaces.
- Inspire participants to take bold steps in innovation and collaboration for development.

The key outcomes were:

- Raised awareness of opportunities available for women and youth in digital R&I.
- Strengthened understanding of strategies to overcome systemic barriers.
- Motivated participants through real-life stories and actionable advice from women innovators.
- Fostered engagement between participants and continental institutions.

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** a total of 31 participants during the session.
- **Gender distribution:** 57,14% were women, 42,86% were men.
- **Average satisfaction rate:** 75% of respondents considered the session “of great interest”, 25% “interesting”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 37,5% considered the session met their needs and expectations “very well”, 50% “well”, 12,5% “well enough”.

6. A Playbook for Research and Innovation Investment: How to Engage Investors and Raise Investment

The virtual bootcamp workshop “A Playbook for Research and Innovation Investment: How to Engage Investors and Raise Investments” was held on the 17th of September 2025 by Methys as the hosts with a number of guest speakers.

The theme and subject matter of virtual bootcamp was based on findings from SEADE’s needs assessment across its four pilot regions, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, and Senegal, which revealed that researchers and innovators struggled in engaging with investors in Africa and raising investments to commercialize their digital IP or innovations. Thus, Methys was tasked with delivering and hosting a virtual bootcamp that would provide a playbook of how researchers and innovators could start their fundraising journeys and engagements with investors and what tools they could use.

The bootcamp workshop was designed to:

- Provide workshop participants with practical knowledge and insights on the investment fundraising journey and what investors are looking for in terms of digital development, IP, innovations and commercialization.
- Provide case studies of digital researchers and innovators who have successfully raised investments and what key takeaways participants can use

- Provide a playbook with tools that researchers and innovators can use to access examples of pitch decks, data rooms, valuations, IP, VC investor data bases, and market profiles for investment in Africa
- Inspire participants to take the fundraising journey through a series of guest speakers consisting of digital innovators who have succeeded in raising investments and VC investors that invest in the digital economy

The key outcomes were to:

- Identify process and roadmap for innovators and researchers to use in the engagement and negotiations with investors in Africa
- Showcase tools and templates that researchers and innovators can use to start their fundraising journeys and engagements with investors
- Inspire participants to take the leap and start building their fundraising roadmap, pitch decks and data rooms
- Foster engagements between researcher/innovators and investors through guest speaker investors

The programme was:

- Session 1: Welcome & Introduction - Speaker: Thomas Hart (Methys)
- Session 2: The Fundraising Journey and Engaging Investors - Speaker: Dan Mabbyalas (AfricArena)
- Session 3: Audience Questions and Answers
- Session 4: Fireside Chat with Christophe Viarnaud (Methys Venture Studio) and Antoine Beyssac (BPI France) - Moderator: Dan Mabbyalas
- Session 5: Audience Questions and Answers

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** a total of 36 participants during the session.
- **Average satisfaction rate:** 66,67% considered the session “of great interest”, 33,33% “interesting”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 66,67% of respondents considered the session met their needs and expectations “very well”, 33,33% “well”.

7. How-to Connect and Develop a Successful Collaboration between EU-SSA Actors

The "How-to Connect and Develop a Successful Collaboration between EU-SSA Actors" virtual bootcamp, organized by the Hapa Foundation in collaboration with the Enrich in Africa Centre (EiAC), European Business and Innovation (EBN), and Bondy Innovation focused on addressing the persistent challenges that limit collaboration, such as navigating cultural differences, overcoming a lack of legal frameworks, and bridging the digital gap. The session provided practical guidance on how to identify partners, navigate funding opportunities, and build strong, long-term relationships. The meeting was convened on September 18, 2025, to provide actionable guidance and foster direct partnerships between actors across the two continents.

The primary objective of this three-hour virtual session was to demystify the process of establishing and sustaining successful EU-SSA partnerships in the context of research and innovation (R&I). The bootcamp served as a practical guide for potential partners, addressing core barriers such as overcoming stereotypes, navigating cultural differences, and understanding the complex legal and administrative frameworks governing collaborative projects.

Through expert presentations and real-world insights, the event aimed to:

- Identify and leverage key areas of synergy (e.g., Digital Transformation, Health, Climate/Agriculture).
- Provide practical, step-by-step guidance on identifying, assessing, and engaging potential partners.
- Equip participants with knowledge on legal, Intellectual Property (IP), and project management best practices for cross-continental grants and agreements.

The programme was as follow:

- The Strategic Importance of EU-SSA Collaboration
- Identifying Synergies and Opportunities
- Practical Guidance on Connecting
- Navigating Cultural Nuances
- Developing Successful Partnerships (Legal Framework)
- Unlocking Funding Opportunities
- Project Management Best Practices

The virtual bootcamp successfully delivered on its core objectives, providing participants with both the strategic vision and the practical tools required to engage effectively in EU-SSA R&I collaborations.

- **Elevated Strategic Understanding:** Participants gained a clear perspective on the "win-win" proposition of EU-SSA collaboration, moving past traditional perceptions to see it as a partnership essential for shared global impact in critical areas like the energy transition and digital transformation.
- **Actionable Roadmap for Partnership:** The sessions provided a detailed, step-by-step roadmap for collaboration, covering everything from proactive partner identification and due diligence to the formal requirements of consortium agreements and IP management.
- **Enhanced Intercultural Competence:** The spotlight on cultural nuances equipped attendees with vital strategies, such as leveraging "connectors" and maintaining high communication transparency, crucial for building trust and managing diverse, geographically dispersed teams.
- **Demystified Funding Landscape:** Attendees received targeted insights into successfully navigating EU funding mechanisms, emphasizing the need for precise proposal writing and the strategic construction of well-balanced consortiums.
- **Strong Community Engagement:** With 81 attendees representing over 10 countries and diverse organizational types (including innovative SMEs, higher education, and digital innovation hubs), the event served as a powerful networking and community-building platform for future SEADE activities.

Here is the main information about the participants:

- **Number of participants:** a total of 56 participants during the session.
- **Average satisfaction rate:** 66,67% of respondents considered the session as “of great interest”, 33,33% “interesting”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 66,67% considered the session met their needs and expectations “very well”, 33,33% “well”.

8. Overall results and achievements

The 5 bootcamp sessions replays have been uploaded on SEADE Youtube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/@SEADEProject>

The combined results are as follows:

- **5 bootcamp sessions** organized within the bootcamp training program.
- Partners involved: Bond’innov, Enrich in Africa Center, AAU, Steinbeis, Hapa, Wazi Up, Methys and BPI.
- 1 391 registration page views
- 497 registrations
- 211 participants in total, including:
 - Navigating Challenges that limit market access for R&IID Innovations in Europe and Africa: **25 participants**
 - Funding Pathways and Practical Strategies for Research & Innovation Actors: **63 participants**
 - Strategies for Youth and Women Empowerment in Digital R&I: **31 participants**
 - A Playbook for Research and Innovation Investment: How African Innovators Can Engage Investors and Raise Investment: **36 participants**
 - How-to Connect and Develop a Successful Collaboration between EU-SSA Actors: **56 participants**

N.B. The presenters, organizers and AI note takers have been excluded from the results.

9. Users’ survey feedback

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, the beneficiaries of the webinars have also reported the following results:

- 27 users’ survey forms received, including :
 - 30% from their participation to Navigating Challenges that limit market access for R&IID Innovations in Europe and Africa session
 - 26% from their participation to Funding Pathways and Practical Strategies for Research & Innovation Actors session
 - 19% from their participation to Navigating Challenges that limit market access for R&IID Innovations in Europe and Africa
 - 15% from their participation to A Playbook for Research and Innovation Investment: How to Engage Investors and Raise Investment

- 11% from their participation to How-to Connect and Develop a Successful Collaboration between EU-SSA Actors.
- **Average satisfaction rate:** 100% of the respondents considered the bootcamp “Of great interest” or “Interesting”.
- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 89% of the respondents considered the webinars fitted their needs “Very well” or “Well”, 11% “well enough”.
- **Country breakdown:** 81% of the respondents were from Africa and 19% from Europe.
- **Organizations:** Among respondents, 52% responded “other,” 9% represented the National Agricultural Research Institute, 9% represented Hapa Space, etc.
- **Gender representation:** 62% were men, 38% were women.
- **Age:** 14% of respondents are 39 years old, and 41% did not specify their age.

E. Digital Youth Training programme

1. Program Overview and Requirements with Timeline

The Digital Youth Training Program was a capacity building program designed to instill digital skills in Youth and Women innovators.

The learning mode was hybrid, that is, it contained both a physical and a virtual component. The physical component was used for hands-on learning, i.e. the participants interacted with the learning materials and tools and were supported by an experienced trainer in the integration of the tools in their solutions. The Virtual component enabled the participants to interact with the self-paced short courses on the Wazilab Learning Platform (<https://lab.waziup.io/orgs/>) through dedicated sessions with a trainer and self-learning by the innovators through the platform. The programs’ goal was to support 20 SSA young entrepreneurs, with a priority on Women, researchers, students and the tech community, to create a startup or prototyping an idea for technology transfer.

The program was piloted in Kenya and Tanzania through pre-selected Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in both countries. The DIH in Kenya was EldoHub and in Tanzania, DTBi. Both Hubs were required to pre-select 5 groups of two participants each to take part in this program. The groups were working on an advanced level IoT or AI solution and wanted to upgrade it and transition it to market.

The solutions were in the area of Water and Irrigation, Agriculture, Bio-Energy or Space-IoT. This took place for one week between the 7th and 11th of April 2025.

An emphasis was placed on Youth and Women to participate in the pre-selection of participants in this event. The Digital Youth Training Program emphasized on supporting innovators in the development of their existing solutions.

2. Deviations from workplan

No deviation from the workplan.

3. Pre-selection

The participating Hubs were pre-selected from the initial network of Hubs from the HUBiquitous (<https://hubiquitous.eu/>) initiative. 5 groups of 2 persons each that had an advanced IoT solution were provided by the Hubs. This list of pre-selected hubs was communicated to WAZIUP e.V. and the Association of African Universities (AAU) for a pre-evaluation and validation. The hubs then shared the program along with the week’s Agenda and prerequisites with the participants. A Solution Box was provided to each of the groups for IoT solution development.

4. Program Agenda

The Digital Youth Training Program ran for one week. The typical structure of this program is given in the table below:

Day	Activity	Description	Instructor
7th April 2025 (10 - 13) CET	Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of Ideas - Introduction to Wazilab - Introduction to the Solution Box - Introduction to IoT 	Joseph & Brian & Isabella & Hubs
	Progress Check	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End of Day Report 	
8th April 2025 (10 - 13) CET	WAZIUP Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WAZISENSE, WAZIGATE and WAZICloud - Example solution - Electronics and Hardware 	Brian
	Progress Check	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End of Day Report 	
9th April 2025 (10 - 13) CET	End Device Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product lifecycle - Edge Computing - Communications and Networking 	Josee
	Progress Check	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End of Day Report 	
10th April 2025 (10 - 12) CET	Web and App development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web and Mobile IoT applications - Data analysis and AI 	Josee
	Progress Check	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End of Day Report 	
11th April 2025 (10 - 12) CET	Business and Market integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Business Support - Product presentations - Analysis of Challenges for Market integration - Feedback on legacy tools - Introduction to the SEADE Digital Environment 	Joseph (WAZI), Isabella (AAU), external partner (Eldohub)
	Report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Program Summary Report 	

Table 6: Agenda of the Digital Youth Training Program

The Digital Youth Training Program (DYTP) began with an introduction to various tools and services that were used in the program. This included the Wazilab platform, the Solution Box and the SEADE Digital environment that contained a list of services developed by the project and integrated to the Enrich in Africa (EiA) Platform to support various needs of the innovators. In this introductory session, the participants were required to present their ideas for evaluation on the stage of development and the level of integration required to complete the solution.

The sessions that followed provided knowledge and skills on WAZIUP Technologies and supported the learners on the integration of these technologies in their solutions. A 3 hour webinar was available daily to guide the participants through the learning materials on the Wazilab platform. This included both technical and non-technical courses and Business support. At the end of each day, participants were required to share a brief report on the activities. An overall report was prepared at the end of the program from the daily summaries. They had 3 days to put this report together and submit it to WAZIUP e.V. and AAU for a final review. WAZIUP e. V. also provided a template for this report which was followed by the participating hubs.

5. Execution and Results

The Wazilab platform was used to train the participants. 3 hour physical sessions were done at the hubs to support the participants on understanding the content and improving their hands-on activities. The remaining hours in the week were used by the participants to self-learn and further prototype their solutions.

The most significant outcome of the Digital Youth Training Program was the improvement of the technical aspects of the participants' innovation. The participants were able to integrate APIs and cloud technologies into their existing solutions, making their products more robust with real-time and remote monitoring features. Through the wazicloud platform, the participants could not only visualise the collected data but also analyse it to draw meaningful insights on the performance of their devices.

Participants who were still at the ideation stage were supported to start the prototyping phase by the use of Waziup hardware. These participants were guided on separate one-on-one sessions where their progress was closely monitored. By the end of the program, the participants had developed basic prototypes for their solutions.

6. Results and achievements

Number of participants: 20 participants (2 persons per group) from Kenya and Tanzania joined the program with basic IoT solutions.

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Region distribution:** 53,8% were from Tanzania, 46,2% were from Kenya.
- **Gender distribution:** 69,2% were men, 30,8% were women. An equal number of women subscribed to the program as men. Since part of the program was conducted physically, 4 women dropped out of the program on the second day and reported financial and road

infrastructure difficulties accessing the venue. The planning team substituted them with an alternative batch of innovators to attend the program.

- **Ages of participants:** 84,6% were between the ages of 18 and 25 years old.
- **Sector coverage:** Majority of the participants in the DYTP came from Innovative SME/Startup/Spinoff and Digital Innovation Hubs.

The results are as follows:

- **Nb. of Countries Covered by Project Activities:** 3 (Kenya, Tanzania, Germany)
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 11 (for each group linked to the market)
- **Nb. of new international collaboration:** 7 (5 for Tanzania and 1 for Germany)
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers..:** 8 experts identified to support business training
- **Nb. of financial partnership:** None

7. Users' survey feedback

Following responses to the satisfaction survey, the beneficiaries of the webinars have also reported the following results (13 users' survey forms received):

- **Meeting needs and expectations:** 69,2% of respondents considered that the activity fitted their needs "very well".
- **Participant confidence on Transitioning Product to Market:** More than 90% of the participants felt confident that the skills gained during the DTYP could help in transitioning their products to the market
- **Participant Feedback on the Ease of access and navigation of Wazilab platform:** More than 80% of the participants found it easy to access and navigate the courses on the Wazilab platform

8. Best practices identified and challenges met

The sessions were conducted in a hybrid format with daily virtual expert-led sessions on Wazilab and in-person training at the DIHs. This training format proved to be successful with participants gaining experience on online tools while improving on team building skills through daily interactions.

Collaboration with the DIHs in Kenya and Tanzania was a good model because there were experts on the ground who were able to support participants during the daily in-person sessions. This format also ensured that all participants could access the hardware through the DIHs.

The challenges experienced include: time constraints where the participants needed more time to fully grasp and apply Waziup technologies such as the Wazigate and the Wazicloud. There was also a low representation of female participants due to bad weather conditions which made it difficult for them to attend the in person training sessions.

9. Translation of DYTP materials into Learning Curricula for Universities, The Wazilab platform - AIoT Route to market (RtoM) program

The DYTP training was conducted on the Wazilab platform (<https://lab.waziup.io/>). The Wazilab platform allows for organizations such as Universities to subscribe and reuse the program for their own AI and IoT training. The program has further been extended to include courses on business and entrepreneurship, market linkage and IP management to support learners on transfer of their solutions to the market. Universities can set up their organization on the platform and reuse the materials to launch the IoT training programs in their organization. As part of the exploitation plan, Waziup will work with the Association of African Universities (AAU) to promote this program in their network.

F. Twinning programme

At its core, the SEADE Twinning programme facilitated partnerships between Research and Innovation in Digital (R&IID) actors from both continents, focusing on fostering sustainable collaboration between European and Sub-Saharan African institutions.

1. Overall presentation

The program operated on a voluntary participation model, aiming to pair at least eight R&IID actors while remaining open to additional matches. A notable feature was the provision of funding for on-site visits for selected pairs, which enables deeper engagement and knowledge exchange. The target participants span research institutes, universities, incubators, and accelerators, creating a diverse ecosystem of innovation partnerships.

The matching process employed a sophisticated approach based on multiple criteria, including expertise alignment, geographic preferences, and organisational type compatibility.

Key areas of expertise exchange included: Technology assessment, Research methodology, Intellectual property management, Business model development, Innovation policy analysis, Commercialisation expertise.

The program demonstrated particular strength in its flexibility, allowing paired organisations to determine their collaboration methods and objectives while maintaining a structured framework for support and monitoring.

Implementation follows a clear four-phase structure:

1. Application processing,
2. Pre-twinning assessment
3. Kick-off meetings,
4. Active collaboration (Possible onsite visits).

A distinct feature was the 2-month milestone review, which served as a checkpoint for evaluating partnership progress and addressing any emerging challenges. While the program mandated certain structural elements like initial presentations and regular check-ins, it maintained flexibility

in how partners collaborate, with optional elements such as Memoranda of Understanding available to formalise relationships.

Looking at the geographic scope, the program explicitly avoided regional restrictions within Sub-Saharan Africa and Europe, promoting inclusive participation across both continents. This approach aligns with the broader SEADE project objectives of creating a seamless "Route-to-Market" pathway for research knowledge and fostering international collaboration in the digital space.

2. Deviations from workplan

No deviations from the workplan.

3. Timeline

Project start: January 1, 2024

Duration: 24 months

Call for applications: Opens September 2024

Continuous pairing process throughout project lifetime

4. Program Timeline and Activities

Timeline	Key Activities	Deliverables
Month 0 (Kickoff)	Initial organisation presentations Objective setting meeting Collaboration planning	Organisation profiles Initial objectives document Optional: Signed MOU
Months 1-3	Regular coordination meetings Knowledge exchange sessions Best practice sharing Joint initiative development	Bi-Monthly progress updates Documentation of exchanges Collaboration roadmap
Months 4-5	Possible Travel Progress evaluation	Travel document preparation Mid-term progress report Best practices documentation

Month 6 (Completion)	Final review meeting Future collaboration planning Program evaluation	Final progress report Future collaboration plan Success stories documentation
-------------------------	---	---

Table 7: Program timeline

5. Call for application

The distribution channels included the SEADE website, social media, and partner platforms.

The application process remained open throughout the entire duration of the project.

The initiative was directed toward research institutes, universities, incubators, and accelerators.

188 applications were received (including 16 from Europe, 167 from Africa).

6. Selection

The selection criteria is based on questionnaire responses.

Matching criteria:

- Expertise alignment
- Geographic preferences
- Type of R&IID actor compatibility
- Mutual interests in collaboration areas

- **Selection Committee**

A selection committee was essential for the SEADE Twinning Program to ensure fair, transparent, and effective matching of organisations. With limited funding for travel (4 pairs) and the need to create sustainable partnerships, objective evaluation is critical. The committee provided expertise to assess compatibility beyond algorithmic matching, considering factors like resource capacity, innovation potential, and long-term collaboration prospects.

Selection Committee Structure:

Composition: SEADE project representatives

Selection Process:

1. Initial screening based on questionnaire responses
2. Evaluation of compatibility scores
3. Assessment of expertise alignment
4. Review of proposed collaboration objectives

Criteria:

- Complementary expertise
- Resource capacity
- Geographic distribution
- Innovation potential
- Commitment to program objectives

The committee will make final decisions on:

- General twinning matches
- Travel funding allocation for 4 selected pairs

The committee meets frequently as needed to review applications and select matches based on established criteria, with focus on sustainable partnerships.

7. Program Structure

The program structure was implemented as presented below:

5. Pre-twinning phase: Initial contact and interest confirmation
6. Kick-off meetings with presentations
7. 6-month collaborative phase
8. Follow-up assessment

8. Monitoring Process

The monitoring process was structured as presented below:

Regular (Months 1-3):

- Bi-monthly updates
- Exchange documentation

Mid-Term (Months 4-5):

- Progress evaluation
- Mid-term report
- Best practices review

Final (Month 6):

- Final review meeting
- Program evaluation

1. Results and achievements

Number of participants: 4 twinning matches (8 organizations total)

Below the profile of the participants:

- **Region distribution:** Kenya, Ghana, Nigeria, Namibia, South Africa, Germany, Luxemburg, Portugal, Lithuania
- **Gender distribution:** Female - 8 ~36% / Male - 14 ~64%
- **Ages of participants:** *(Most participants are institutional leaders, researchers, managers.)*

Age Group	Notes
30–39	Early-career leads, programme managers
40–55+	Majority of institutional leads (professors, CEOs, directors)

Estimated spread:

- 30–39 years: ~30%
- 40–55 years: ~70%
- **Sector coverage:** 7 sectors covered (Innovation & Startup Ecosystems, Technology and ICT, Agriculture and AgriTech, Energy & CleanTech, Women’s Economic Empowerment, Research & Academia).

The results are as follows (on 28/11/2025 - the twinning programme is still ongoing until end of M24):

- **Nb. of Countries Covered by Project Activities:** 11 (Kenya, Ghana, Nigeria, Namibia, South Africa, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Germany, Portugal, Spain, Belgium)
- **Nb. of New International Collaboration:** 8
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** 5
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers.. :** 3
- **Nb. of financial partnership:** 5

Current Status (from twinning-matches):

- Multiple potential matches identified
- High compatibility scores (80-95%)
- Diverse sector representation (education, sustainability, technology)
- Strong EU-AU and AU-AU matching potential

1. Users’ survey feedback

Overall Satisfaction: 92%. Partners across all twins reported high usefulness, relevance, and value from the twinning activities.

Main Positives Identified

- Very valuable knowledge exchange

- Strong collaboration with twin institutions
- Productive meetings and well-structured engagements
- Significant networking and exposure during Brussels & Luxembourg/other visits
- Clear progress toward joint programmes and future collaboration

11. Best practices and challenges met

The main challenges met are the following:

- Visa delays and denials affected travel plans
- Tight travel timelines reduced time for deeper engagement

G. R&I to Industry Match-Making Activities

Leveraging the Enrich in Africa EuroQuity community, Bpifrance organized targeted activities such as e-pitching sessions, investor reverse pitches, webinars, and matchmaking events to support collaboration, while also creating a new SEADE label dedicated to research focused companies and organisations. These actions connected R&I and innovation development (R&IID) actors with companies, investors, accelerators, and incubators. Through these opportunities, R&IID actors showcase their portfolios, build industry relationships, and develop international partnerships in research and technology transfer, helping ensure investor engagement and market expansion.

1. Deviations from workplan

No deviation from the workplan.

2. Overall timeline

The activities of T4.2 took place in two different phases: the first one investigating the ecosystem and building awareness about the SEADE program, and the second deploying activities to help Africa's research based startups meet with partners and investors.

Phase 1: M1–M12 (Jan–Dec 2024)

Focus: Initial setup, first events, and SEADE label creation.

- Created SEADE label (July 18, 2024) and onboarded 74 organizations.
- Reverse Pitch #1 (Oct 23, 2024)
- Pitch Session #1 (Dec 11, 2024)

Phase 2: M13–M18 (Jan–Nov 2025)

Focus: Scaling activities, platform development, and second events.

- Onboarded 27 more organizations (total: 101).
- Reverse Pitch #2
- Pitch Session #2
- SEADE Pitching Startups Booklet

- VivaTech Afterwork (Jun 12, 2025)
- Reverse Pitch #3 (Sep 11, 2025)
- Pitch Session #3 (Sep 25, 2025)
- Reverse Pitch #4 (Oct 16, 2025)
- Pitch Session #4 (Nov 26, 2025)

3. Detail of the activities

Bpifrance’s EuroQuity team organized targeted events and webinars to enable matchmaking between R&IID actors and key stakeholders. It delivered 4 e-pitching sessions and 4 investor reverse pitches. It facilitated investor contacts, and supported market expansion through an event organised in Paris during the VivaTech summit, the publication of a portfolio booklet, and the creation and animation of a dedicated label on the EuroQuity matchmaking platform.

Because the matchmaking activities under T4.2 differ greatly, this report is divided among activities and sessions, for improved clarity.

● E-pitching sessions

E-pitches sessions are the opportunities for scalable solutions to be presented to potential investors. Startups are selected and coached by Bpifrance’s EuroQuity team and investors invited through the EuroQuity network.

Timeline

Session	Date	Notes
E-Pitch 01	11 Dec 2024	First SEADE Pitching Session
E-Pitch 02	24 Apr 2025	Second SEADE Pitching Session
E-Pitch 03	25 Sep 2025	Third SEADE Pitching Session
E-Pitch 04	26 Nov 2025	Fourth SEADE Pitching Session in partnership with the Innovation Fair

Table 8: Timeline

Process

1. Pre-event (4–6 weeks)
 - a. Sourcing & Call for Applications (EuroQuity, EiA, partners)
 - b. Pipeline creation & screening (eligibility + fit with SEADE goals)
 - c. Selection roundtable → shortlist 5 startups
 - d. Onboarding & preparation
 - i. 1:1 Mock Pitches for each founder
 - ii. Followup emails to refine decks (storyline, ask, KPIs)
 - iii. Create event links (Teams/YouTube) & calendar invites
2. Event day (60–75 min)

- a. Opening (5') – quick reminder of SEADE objectives
- b. Founder pitches (5' each) + Q&A (2' each) — 5 startups
- c. Live moderation & housekeeping (slides order, polls/surveys)
- d. Postevent (T+1 to T+10 days)
- e. Export data (attendance reports) + consolidate introduction requests
 - 1. Warm intros (email) between investors & startups
 - 2. Follow-up: capture outcomes (interest, NDAs, due diligence, PoCs, term sheets)

● **Results and achievements**

Session	EPitch 01	EPitch 02	E-Pitch 03	E-Pitch 04
Date	11 Dec 2024	24 Apr 2025	25 Sep 2025	26 Nov 2025
Applicants (startups)	22	20	12	-*
Selected to pitch	5	5	5	6
Selection rate	22.7%	25.0%	41.7%	-
Investors - registered	137	65	32	13
Investors - attended	44	17	10	4
Attendance rate	32%	26%	31%	31%
Introductions made	19	7	1	5
Introductions per startups (avg/med/max)	4 / 4 / 5	1/1/3	0/0/1	1/1/2
Investors region mix	43% Africa / 39% Europe / 18% other	50% Africa / 39.06% Europe / 10.94% other	30% Africa / 60% Europe / 10% other	53% Africa / 47% Europe

* For its 4th e-pitch session, the SEADE project collaborated with DG RTD's Innovation Fair to offer a pitching slot to the winners of the event. Hence, no application process has been opened.

Table 9: E-Pitch results

Pitching startups

- E-Pitch 01 (Dec 11, 2024): ATAREC (Morocco), Chestify (Ghana), MScan (Uganda), APIsentry (Nigeria), Bixbio (South Africa)
- E-Pitch 02 (Apr 24, 2025): Aerial Metric (Madagascar), Pixii Motors (Tunisia), BPhage (South Africa), Sawubona Mycelium (South Africa), Elakistos Biosciences (Kenya)
- E-Pitch 03 (Sep 25, 2025): Sand to Green (France), DeepLeaf (Morocco), Acecore Incorporations (Nigeria), Evonet Energy (Kenya), ArborX (Zimbabwe)

- E-Pitch 04 (Nov 26, 2025): Gene4All (Spain), Venth Ventures Limited (Nigeria), LUXEED Robotics (Netherlands), Astrosit Technology Inc. (Türkiye), Telemedan (Chad), K'wezi.Midwife (Rwanda)

Gender balance

The diversity of teams applying to the pitches has been taken into account, but due to the relative scarcity of female researchers and entrepreneurs, and to the scarcity of female CEOs, only 28% of the pitchers were women.

- **Reverse-pitches**

Reverse-pitches are organised for researchers and entrepreneurs to better understand the needs and expectations of investors. Investors and acceleration program managers come to pitch their funds' investment thesis and answer questions from entrepreneurs.

Timeline

- Reverse Pitch #1: 23 Oct 2024
- Reverse Pitch #2: 26 Feb 2025
- Reverse Pitch #3: 11 Sep 2025
- Reverse Pitch #4: Oct 16, 2025

Process

1. Pre-event
 - a. Identify and invite investors to present their investment thesis.
 - b. Email campaigns to startups and investors.
 - c. Prepare agenda, harmonize investor order, create Teams event link.
2. Event
 - a. 1-hour session.
 - b. Investors present their thesis (5–10 min each).
 - c. Q&A and open discussion with startups.
3. Post-event
 - a. Export attendance data.
 - b. Share recordings and materials.
 - c. Facilitate introductions between interested parties.

- **Results and achievements**

Session	Reverse Pitch #1	Reverse Pitch #2	Reverse Pitch #3	Reverse Pitch #4
Date	23 Oct 2024	26 Feb 2025	11 Sep 2025	Oct 16, 2025
Investors presenting	3	3	2	2
Startups registered	97	77	41	79
Startups attended	59	23	19	29
Attendance rate	61%	29%	46%	34%

Table 10: Reverse pitch results

Gender balance

Gender parity has been respected in the selection of the speakers for the reverse pitches, with 50% men and 50% women pitching their activities.

Speakers	Male	Female
Reverse Pitch #1	2	1
Reverse Pitch #2	0	3
Reverse Pitch #3	1	1
Reverse Pitch #4	2	0
Total	5	5

Table 11: Gender balance table

Other matchmaking activities

Bpifrance’s EuroQuity team implemented various additional matchmaking activities to facilitate connections with ecosystem players. These activities have been complemented by support to entrepreneurs in setting up and using their EuroQuity profiles.

Timeline

- SEADE VivaTech Afterwork, 12 June 2025
- SEADE Pitching Startups Booklet, June 2025
- SEADE Label Onboarding, Jul 2024 – Dec 2025

Process

1. VivaTech Afterwork (June 12, 2025)

1. Target audience: African startups, investors, ecosystem partners, tech community.
2. Promotion: Email campaigns, branded registration form, reminders.
3. Logistics: Bpifrance rooftop, catering, name tags, photowall.
4. Engagement: On-site networking, team-facilitated introductions, photos/videos captured.
5. Follow-up: Highlights emailed to attendees, collaboration opportunities shared.

2. SEADE Pitching Startups Booklet

1. Content: Startup profiles from all SEADE pitch sessions.
2. Data collected: Tech description, sector, funding goals, team bios, traction.
3. Verification: Direct outreach to startups for accuracy.
4. Distribution: Emailed to 500+ investors.

3. SEADE Label Onboarding

1. Platform: EuroQuity.
2. Size: 101 organizations.
3. Purpose: Build a curated pool of SEADE-aligned startups and partners.

4. Main results and achievements

Metric	Value
VivaTech Afterwork – Registrations	281
VivaTech Afterwork – Confirmed attendees	168
VivaTech Afterwork – Attendees presents	55
SEADE Label – onboarded organisations	101
Pitching Startups Booklet – Distribution	100+ unique visitors

Table 12: R&I matchmaking activities main results

● Overall results

While not directly targeting collaboration in R&I, the matchmaking activities contributed to SEADE’s overall expected results.

- **Nb. of Countries Covered by Project Activities:** 15 (Morocco, Ghana, Uganda, Nigeria, South Africa, Madagascar, Tunisia, Kenya, France, Zimbabwe, Spain, Netherlands, Türkiye, Chad, Rwanda.)
- **Nb. of collaboration in R&I:** N/A
- **Nb. of new international collaboration:** N/A
- **Nb. of recruitment of experts, researchers..:** 101 organisations onboarded on the SEADE label on EuroQuity
- **Nb. of financial partnership:** 32 introductions of entrepreneurs made by the EuroQuity team to interested investors, more were organically fostered.

● Satisfaction survey’s feedback

Very few participants answered satisfaction surveys but existing feedback is largely positive.

- **Gender Representation:** 66.7% of respondents identified as male, while 33.3% identified as female.
- **Beneficiary Categories:** Half of the respondents (50%) belonged to the “Innovative SME/Startup/Spinoff” category, 33.3% to “Digital Innovation Hub,” and 16.7% to “Incubator related to academia or research institute.”

- **Interest in Service:** 83.3% of respondents considered the service “of great interest,” while 16.7% found it “interesting.”
- **Meeting Needs and Expectations:** 33.3% of respondents considered that the activity fitted their needs “very well,” 50% said “well,” and 16.7% said “not at all.”
- **Organization Quality:** 66.7% rated the activity as “very well organized,” 16.7% as “well,” and 16.7% as “well enough.”
- **Impact on Project Realization:** Only 16.7% of respondents reported that the activity helped transform a project into reality, while 83.3% said it did not.

The R&I to Industry Match-Making Activities under the SEADE program have successfully connected research and innovation actors with key industry stakeholders, fostering collaboration and market expansion. Through targeted events such as e-pitching sessions, reverse pitches, webinars, and matchmaking activities, Bpifrance has facilitated meaningful interactions between startups, investors, and ecosystem partners. The SEADE label, dedicated to research-focused companies, has further strengthened these connections, supporting 101 organizations across 15 countries.

The program, executed in two phases, has delivered tangible results, including 4 e-pitching sessions, 4 reverse pitches, and a portfolio booklet distributed to over 500 investors. While gender representation remains a challenge, the activities have received largely positive feedback, with participants expressing high satisfaction and interest in the services provided. Overall, the matchmaking efforts have contributed significantly to SEADE’s goal of fostering international partnerships and investor engagement in the African research and innovation ecosystem.

Conclusion

The Route-to-Market activities carried out as part of the SEADE project have contributed significantly to structuring and strengthening bridges between European and African research and innovation ecosystems. The combination of awareness-raising, capacity-building, networking and market access support actions has had a tangible impact on the mobility, collaboration and visibility of R&I actors in the four pilot regions.

The results achieved demonstrate the relevance of the multi-instrumental approach adopted, despite persistent challenges, particularly in terms of female participation, mobility logistics and post-programme engagement. The lessons learned from this cycle of activities will help improve the design and deployment of future initiatives, in particular by strengthening gender mainstreaming, the quality of partnership monitoring and the territorial anchoring of actions.

The project has demonstrated the capacity of the regions involved to host innovative programmes, generate concrete opportunities for collaboration and attract the interest of investors and institutional actors. The overall results reinforce the momentum that has been built up and provide a solid basis for continuing cooperation between the European Union and sub-Saharan African countries in the field of digital technology, research and innovation.